
UNIVERSITY OF THE EAST GRADUATE SCHOOL

**HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT ON
EMPLOYEE'S PERFORMANCE AND
PRODUCTIVITY IN SELECTED
CONSTRUCTION COMPANIES**

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the Graduate School of the University of the East**

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for the Degree of Master of Science in
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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the historical and contextual background of the problem, hypothesis, contextual framework, statement of the problem, significance of the study, scope and delimitation and operational definition of terms.

1.1 Background of the Study

Human resources has an important role in any company because even if a company can have a lot of money and good information with best machines but if the level of manpower is poor, the company can't work with enough productivity. The management of organization in a globalized economy is posing a serious challenge to the leadership skills, capability and competency of managers at the top level of the firms in achieving proper productivity and profitability.

According to Sullivan (2011), "global competition has created a rapid pace of change which means that current skill sets must be continually updated. It is the manager's job to identify the employees with less optimal skills". HR's role is to develop processes to continually increase employee learning, knowledge, and skill development while minimizing the amount of time that employees are away from their work to get more productivity in the companies. The companies must compete with other companies in order to increase

profitability and productivity. Training and manpower development is one of the ways to achieve this goal. Human resources being the most dynamic of all the organizations resources are needed considerably by the organizations management, if it has to realize its full potentials at work. Therefore, motivation, leadership, communication, work restructuring, payment system (compensation) as well as training and development may all be included in the issues which have to be dealt by management of today. Human resource development in construction project have played a significant role in the economic development in most developed countries such as the United States of America, Britain and Japan among others.

The definitions of HRD key components demonstrate the multi-disciplinary nature of the field and include behavioral change, adult learning (formal and informal), performance (human, organizational, individuals level, work process), performance improvement, organizational and personal goals development (career and organizational), training and development, learning, learning climate, and learning organizations. Key definitions have a variety of underlying theories including psychological, systems, economic, philosophical, human performance, organizational performance, and performance system. While a wide variety of perspectives in the field of HRD can provide a view that is not limiting, it can also create too broad a field.

Organizations that intend to grow and sophisticate utilize an extensive portion of their resources in human resource development. Human resource development is directed towards changing an organization and everyone associated with it from within, in order to gain advantage over its competitors and ultimately achieving great amount of success. It also caters to the need for employee talent and skill development within an organization.

Construction projects can improve and increase the firm performance by human resource development in a proper system for companies that is so much important for managers and owners of construction companies to know and analyze those factors which existed and conflicted the performance of HRD on employee's performance and productivity in the projects and then attempting to improve them.

There are cases in the industry that shows us the human resource development had a lot of advantages and effectiveness such as increasing profit, productivity and improvement of performance for company and the people who are included in any organization, without a proper instructional system, they cannot be efficient to get its targets. According to the Philippines Constructors Association, for the past 40 years, it has accounted for about five percent (5%) of the economy's total output on the average. In the last five years, the percentage share of the Philippines construction industry to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) has averaged around four to five percent (4-5%).

The Philippines construction industry, indeed, is of great importance to the country's economy. Its contributions span extensive to other sectors of the economy. This significance provides enough incentive to develop it further in order to accelerate the country's economic growth. The construction industry is considered one of the most important sectors that contributes significantly to the country's economic output in the Philippines, generates considerable number of jobs, brings in large investments, and gains in foreign exchange earnings. Considering its multiplier effect, the industry enhances the growth of other industries directly.

According to Lethi and Aillam (2005) since 1986, the Philippine economy is within the period of active trade liberalization and globalization. However, it seems that globalization and trade liberalization brought about capital-intensive industrial structure to the country. Within industrial structure, manufacturing, is commonly considered as the main provider of employment with adequate quality has even decreasing importance in the economy, which has reduced its share from total output from 23.9% in the period 1986-1989 to 22.2% in 2000 and 23% in 2003. Also, productivity indicators that are available in the Philippine literatures show poor performance.

But broadly for the whole country in the Philippines, the quality of employment opportunities seem to be low, as indicated by the share of manufacturing employment to the total, which is lower than other ASEAN countries. According to the Philippine Constructors Association, there are several opportunities by which the country can

move forward with the help of the construction industry. The main recommendations specified in this Roadmap are critical to the development and enhancement of the industry's competitiveness, and require strong support from the government to realize this objective. That is why government must lead organizations for improving the performances of companies in the Philippines to an acceptable level by using proper methods and ways as improvement of HR that is essential for the country.

According to Divina (2007) there are a number of reasons cited in the survey as to why human resource development is important in the Philippine companies, and it is realized that the value of “improvement of job performance” (95.83%), tops the list and the other more frequently identified values of the importance of human resource development from a bigger bulk of the firms. Other values are: “helps improve and acquire technical skills” (91.67%), “develops creativity and problem-solving skills” (89.17%), “helps retain a competent and efficient workforce” (89.17%), “helps achieve overall organizational objectives” (88.33%), and “contributes to flexibility in order to adapt to changes” (80.83%). But the information shows most of the companies in the Philippines still have a lot of problems concerning HRM, and the managers do not realize the importance of having efficient manpower and improving HR as one of the key elements of being successful to achieve their targets in any organization like the construction industry. Particularly, most organizations have inefficient knowledge how to promote their employees according to their needs by proper methods and practices as training and motivation.

Unfortunately, the management of some organizations do not seem to know the importance of human resource development on employee's performance and productivity. "HR professionals acknowledge that their job entails establishing policy, procedures, and programs governing people management for training but there are few attempts to connect such elements to increasing employee output (volume, speed and quality) per each dollar spent on labor costs (or as an easier to measure alternative, revenue per employee)" (Sullivan, 2011). It appears that human resource development in some of the construction companies is haphazard, unplanned and unsystematic, and several of its employees such as machine operators, middle level engineers, account clerks, computer operators and many other category of workers, have not qualified for any form of human resource development nor is there any systematic process of staff development in place. And some management believes that if workers have acquired university education, there is no need to train again. Provisions of welfare facilities are not given adequate attention in some organization. One of the important elements to human resource development is manpower training, according to the employers in the Philippines, whether in the private sector or in government, believe that an investment in education and training that are a part of HRD is the key to raising profitability and productivity in the workplace (which necessitates the development of skills and competencies of workers), and should lead to a sustained increase in labor incomes. The employers, on their end, provide trainings to meet their needs through their respective companies. There is a need to improve the educational programs and to upgrade the skills standards in order to

ensure continuous supply of globally competitive construction professionals (e.g. architect, engineers, technicians, etc.) and highly productive workers.

There are some challenges in construction companies for accomplishment of training and increasing knowledge of staffs that are part of HRD. In 2005-2006, U.S. Construction Industry Training Report offers insights into how organizations are handling these challenges by developing future leaders, measuring the results of their training programs, and focusing on a high-performance workforce” (Kelley, 2006).

At the 2008 International Labor Conference (ILO) there was a suggestion to employers and workers to adopt a set of conclusions squarely focused on this challenge. These conclusions provide practical guidance for strengthening education, training and lifelong learning as central pillars of employability for workers and sustainability for enterprises within the Decent Work Agenda to increase productivity.

In the U.S., construction contracting business is faced with various problems remaining competitive both at home and in the international construction market” (Nunnally, 2001). Productivity is one of the most critical goals in any business. The reduction of productivity that happened by challenges in construction companies can reduce construction’s share of the U.S. gross national product (Nunnally, 2001). One of the ways that can help the companies solve those challenges is enforcement of an efficient HRD. Surveys of the top 400 US contractors were

conducted in 1979, 1983 and 1993 to identify the areas with potentials for productivity improvement in the construction industry (Arditi, 2003).

Also the results of the surveys showed that labor training was one of the elements to improve productivity and profit in any company. In 1995-2006, there was an overall increase in participation rates in training by 20 percent. The participation rate in training was calculated by dividing the number of workers who participated in any form of training activity. This was associated with an overall increase in productivity of 4 percent (from £27,328 in 1995 to £28,391 in 2006 – at 2003 prices), (Patrick and Ison, 2008). According to Black and Lynch (1996) who used a large longitudinal survey of US construction, that provided training input figures for 1990 and 1993. They found in construction a positive association between enterprise productivity levels and time spent by employees in formal, off the job training.

As organizations strive to compete in the global economy, differentiation on the basis of the skills, knowledge, and motivation of their workforce takes an increasing importance. Furthermore, according to a recent industry report by the American Society for Training and Development (ASTD), U.S. organizations alone spend more than \$126 billion annually on human resource development to increase profit and productivity (Paradisén, 2007). There were researches, studies and surveys around the world that have concerned effectiveness of HRD on improving employee's performance and construction's productivity, and researchers were

interested about this issue as a key element for owners of the companies to obtain more profit by establishing proper HRD in the organization.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

This paper attempts to investigate the impact of human resource development on employee's performance and productivity in selected construction companies in Metro Manila.

The specific questions to be answered by the proposed research are as follows:

1. What is the level of awareness of the respondents concerning human resource development in increasing employee's performance, productivity and company profit in the selected construction companies in Metro Manila as perceived by the respondents?
2. What are the prospects and challenges of human resource development on employee's performance and productivity in selected construction companies in Metro Manila?
3. What are the efficient methods for evaluating employee's performance and productivity to analyze and understand the influences of human resource development in the construction industry?

1.3 Conceptual Framework

Based on the presentation of the theoretical framework of the study, the researcher has conceptualized the paradigm of the investigation and evaluation with the performance of the theory of “input-process-output”, as shown in Figure 1.

As reflected in Figure 1, the flow of the study starts with the personnel organizational profile variables of the company-respondents of selected individual (engineer, manager and other experts) in construction companies in Metro Manila, Philippines. This includes the respondent's profile, training system used status, types of assessment effects of training system in construction industry and important factors perceived to be factors effected by human resource development on employee's performances and productivity in construction companies.

The process involves the level of awareness of the respondents concerning human resource development and its influences on employee's performance and productivity, and identification of the Influences of human resource development on employee's performance and productivity in construction company. Through the process it is intended to identify and evaluate the human resource development, and also aspects of implementing this system in construction companies in Metro Manila, Philippines. The main aim of this study is to determine the prospects, challenges and benefits of implementing human resource development concerning the productivity and employee's performances in the selected construction companies in Metro Manila.

And finally, comprehensive issue is focused on the human resource development and its effectiveness on employee's performance and productivity in construction companies in Metro manila, Philippines.

FIGURE 1 Conceptual Framework

1.4. Research Hypothesis

In this study, the following research (null) hypothesis were tested:

- 1.4.1 There is no significant difference on the implementation of HRD and employee's performance on the performance and capability of the respondents ten (10) selected construction companies in Metro Manila.
- 1.4.2 There is no significant difference on the implementation of HRD and productivity on the performance and capability of the respondents ten (10) selected construction companies in Metro Manila.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The proposed study is a unique construction technique undertaken by the researcher which has a tremendous impact on the construction industry as it continues to evolve toward adoption of sophisticated construction projects and to meet the project owners' needs as they seek to maximize their target employee's performance and productivity. It also has an impact to the human resource in the construction industry for improvement of employee's skills and attitude to become more competitive and productive in the management of the construction companies.

The outcomes and findings of this study would benefit the construction companies in the implementation of their program in relation to the human resource

development in the construction industry. The findings of this study would greatly benefit the project owner and contractor, who may have different perception on construction system, and the HRD which plays a major role in helping them to improve the effectiveness of construction's system and project quality. Human resource development can solve a variety of manpower problems against optimum productivity and employee's performance. Included are operating problems having a manpower component. The research may have particular significance to groups of individuals and corporate organizations and institutions as follows:

1. Project owners who wanted to minimize cost and time while ensuring that employees have enough ability to perform their jobs with high quality and productivity.
2. Managers who wanted to introduce modern schemes for HRD, for improving their HR to approach the targets of organization, and also to be able to meet the challenges of change in the future.
3. Contractors who wanted to finish their projects in the shortest possible time of good quality and without delays so that they can increase their profit.
4. Employees who possess useful skills and knowledge which enhance their value, increasing their job security and wage in their companies.
5. HRM that would help the company to identify needs in improving manpower in the company.

6. Companies that can get more profit indirectly and then company achieve profit a few times more than expenses of the human resource development.
7. Consultants who to look for improvement of companies by implementing human resource development for construction projects.
8. University offering engineering related courses with subject/s about efficient utilization of HR and implementing human resource development to improve profit, employee's performance and productivity in construction industry or other industries.
9. Professionals who plan to seek new construction techniques to increase and update their technical knowledge.
10. Students who should become familiar with new methods and strategies concerning human resource development as a part of HRM, and data obtained from this study may open other areas for future researchers in the HR area in construction industry.

1.6 Scope and Delimitation

As the construction industry continues to evolve, HR also continues in implementing human resource development for Project Owners, Managers, Engineers and others experts to achieve their goals, saving a lot of project resources and most importantly, saving a lot of money. This research study is

limited to human resource development in construction industry and focused on the evaluation of the impact of human resource development for employees and companies in selected construction companies in Metro Manila, Philippines. The time frame of this study was 2013 – 2014 inclusive. The respondents of this study are limited to (10) selected construction companies that were classified (AAA) in Metro Manila, Philippines and have implemented human resource development in their private construction projects in the past, current and future time.

This study is primarily identification and determination of impact of human resource development on employee's performance and productivity in selected construction companies in Metro Manila, Philippines. Since the study focuses on the introduction of human resource development and its aspects, the researcher used the survey questionnaire and interview method in gathering necessary information about the impact of human resource development on employee's performance and productivity in selected construction companies in Metro Manila, Philippines.

In this study, a total of ten (10) construction companies category (AAA) were surveyed. And from each company five (5) persons which includes project managements staffs, supervisors, engineers, accountants, consultants and others experts were randomly selected to answer the survey questionnaires.

1.7 Operational Definition of Terms

Ability. The quality of being able to perform; a quality that permits or facilitates achievement.

Culture. Culture is a pattern of shared basic assumptions that was learned by a group as it solved its problems of external adaptation and internal integration, that has worked well enough to be considered valid and, therefore, to be taught to new members as the correct way to perceive, think, and feel in relation to those problems.

Development. Development is an activity designed to improve the performance of existing managers and to provide for a planned growth of managers to meet future organizational requirements is management development.

Development Training. Development training is combination of the concepts of development (change and growth) and training (learning specific skills) together.

Employment. refers to remunerative work either for an employer or self-employment.

Employee's Performance. The job related activities expected of a worker and how well those activities were executed.

Employee productivity. Employee productivity is an outcome of the employee's knowledge, capability, motivation, workplace environment, etc. Generally, productivity is defined as output gained from the fixed amount of inputs.

Human Resource (HR). The resource that resides in the knowledge, skills, and motivation of people. It is therefore regarded as the scarcest and most crucial productive resource that creates the largest and longest advantage for an organization.

HRD. Human Resources Development (HRD) as a theory is a framework for the expansion of human capital within an organization through the development of both the organization and the individual to achieve performance improvement.

HRM. Is defined as a contributory factor in the employment relationship analysis, a sponsor of a whole new relationship between management and employees implying recruitment, selection, learning and development, reward, communication and performance management.

Knowledge. The psychological result of perception and learning and reasoning.

Manpower. It is that portion of the population which has actual or potential capability to contribute to the production of goods and services.

Organizational Development. Is comprises the actual output or results of an organization as measured against its intended output or goals and objectives.

Performance. The use of the word performance as it applies in this case means the execution of an action, something accomplished, the fulfillment of a claim, promise, or request, implementation.

Productivity. Productivity can be simply illustrated by an association between an output and an input. Two forms of productivity were used in previous studies and in the industry :

- 1) productivity = output ÷ Input and , or sometimes is computed as
- 2) productivity = input ÷ output.

Profit. The excess of revenues over outly in a given period of time (including depreciation and other non – cash expenses – taxes).

Satisfaction.The use of the word satisfaction as it applies in this case means the fulfillment of a need or want, the quality or state of being satisfied, a source or means of enjoyment.

Training. Training is the act of increasing the skills of an employee for doing a particular job. Training program focused more on preparation for improved performance in particular job.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter presents the literature that has significant relationship in the present study and further explains and supports the relationship of the variables in the study. Moreover, it presents the established similarities between the studies compared.

2.1 Related Literature

The literature attempts to estimate the possible impact of human resource development on employee's performance and productivity in construction industry. It is an initial investigation into this area. Also, this study tries to find out the effectiveness of human resource development on employees and companies.

Human Resource Development (HRD) is the domain that performs core function in an organization for the advancement of personal and professional skills, knowledge and abilities of employees. Human resource development includes such opportunities as employee training, employee career development, performance management and development, coaching, mentoring, succession planning, key employee identification and organization development. HRD has the key role in improving knowledge and skills on human resource in any organization. HR professionals are very important for the organization. The main target of human

resource development is on fostering the workforce so that the company as well as employees can achieve their work goals and objective to maximum satisfaction.

The companies implement a planned development of human resources needed for the company to grow and actively support their employees in the voluntary development of their skills with the aim of achieving growth for both the company and our employees.

Nowadays, managers believe that the employees are the most important management resources. Managers are aiming to achieve growth for both the company and employees by actively supporting the growth of each individual employee and developing human resources who are equipped with skills and experience required to work at the organization.

Managers approach human resources development from the three areas such as:

- 1) Planned Human Resource Development which is to implement planned development to foster and secure the human resources needed to achieve the management vision (e.g., growth strategy, business continuity, creation of corporate culture);
- 2) Skill Development which is tasked to develop on individual employees their skills and increase their market value, and;

- 3) Career Development which is a continuous lifelong process of developmental experiences that focus on seeking, obtaining and processing information about self, occupational and educational alternatives, life styles and role options support medium to long-term career development and promote growth toward employees' ideals.

According to Figure 2, HRD aims to promote comprehensive education incorporating the perspectives of training system, On-the-Job Training (OJT), medium to long-term career path development of human resource systems to support these programs.

Figure 2 Human Resources Development Model

Organizations have many opportunities for human resources or employee development, both within and outside of the workplace. Human Resource Development can be both ceremonial as well as casual ranging from classroom training sessions and college course and an organizational scheduled change effort to casual mentoring of subordinates by their superiors. Organizations that intend to grow and become sophisticate utilize an extensive portion of their resources in human resource development.

Human resource development is directed towards changing an organization and everyone associated with it from within, in order to gain advantage over its competitors and ultimately achieving great amount of success. It also caters the need for employee talent and skill development within an organization. Talent and skills development are important components of Human Resource Development. Equipping employees with technical skills that are required to perform specific tasks with soft skills such as leadership, communication, time management and others actually enhances the performances of these individuals and ultimately benefits the organization in the long run. This also adds to employee satisfaction, as learning something new boosts up their energy level and not only makes them better employees but rather better human beings.

More and more companies are acquainting themselves with concepts of talent development or training and development from HRD. Talent development accumulates a vast array of elements such as organizational development, training

and development, career development and the workplace management and etc. There is an increasing need for individuals to take charge of the development of their own learning and careers for a variety of reasons and also there is an increasing rate of change of the organizations and in the knowledge and skills. Top management and executives need to genuinely realize the strategic importance of HRD as a value-added source for sustained competitive advantage. Human resource managers who were in charge of the design and implementation of the business development needed to focus on the corporate business vision and long-term growth strategies to get more productivity and profit for their companies.

There are numerous factors affecting employee's performance and productivity in construction site and generally these factors are manifested to affect in the construction at large. There are also several factors that influence employee's performance and productivity in construction company. "Productivity improvement in construction is best understood when the construction process is visualized as a complete system" (Dozzi and AbouRizk, 1993), as shown in Figure 3, the system is made up of the construction project.

Figure 3 Modified Framework Improvement of Firm Performance in Construction

According to Figure 3, the construction system can be described as an IPO (Input, Process, Output) system. There are four elements in Input (Machine, Materials, Methods, Manpower) of this system and Manpower is the most important factor among them and the organization can use and consume properly other factors are left by promoting and improving HR or manpower, and human resource development is the main way to achieve this target (improving HR).

This system shows the stages of improving HR by HRD through construction project system HRD can cause improving step by step firm performance in construction company, these stages are included:

1. Improvement of HR outcome: Improved knowledge, ability, skills, employee's behaviour;
2. Improvement of organization performance outcome: Non-financial performance (employee's satisfaction, time, absence, change of organization culture, increasing revenue);
3. The increase of productivity and finally;
4. The increase of financial outcome: improved profitability.

Finally, improvement of skills and behaviour of employees help change both employees and companies in a good situation. Clearly, HRD can generate more efficiency for staffs and the company toward improving employee's performance and the company productivity.

Much researches into HRD were concerned with the effectiveness of training on the companies and employees.

This study tried to find and realize all factors which are caused by HRD on productivity and employee's performance in construction industry, for getting this aim the researcher used recent local and foreign studies about the impact human resource development on productivity and employee's performance in construction companies. HRD can be both ceremonial as well as casual ranging from classroom training sessions and college courses, and an organizational scheduled change effort, to casual mentoring of subordinates by their superiors. Organizations that intend to grow and sophisticate utilize an extensive portion of their resources in Human Resource Development which is directed towards changing an organization and everyone associated with it from within, in order to gain advantage over its competitors and ultimately achieving great amount of success. It also caters the need for employee talent and skill development within an organization.

Talent and Skills Development are important components of human resource development. To equip employees, alongside technical skills that are required to perform specific tasks, with soft skills such as leadership, communication, time management and so on and so forth actually enhances the performances of these individuals ultimately benefiting the organization in the long run. This also adds to employee satisfaction, as learning something new boots up their energy level and not only makes them better employees but rather better human beings.

These more and more companies are acquainting themselves with concepts of talent development or training and development. Talent development accumulates a vast array of elements such as organizational development, training and development, career development and workplace management and etc. It is said that during the 21st century more organizations will be focusing on talent management and development.

Human resource development as a process occurs within employees and organizations:

- 1) Training and Development (TD): The development of human expertise for the purpose of improving employee's performance;
- 2) Organizational Development (OD): Empowering the organization to take advantage of its human resource capital;

The companies should improve continually employee's skills and attitude to ensure enforcing optimal performance in the workplace.

Training and Development in Construction Industry

Nowadays, organizations know proper training needs to establish a proper system. Training is referred to as a systematic approach to learning and development to improve individual, team, and organizational effectiveness (Goldstein and Ford 2002). Training is the systematic development of the attitude and skill

behavior pattern required by an individual in order to perform adequately a given task. “It is also the systematic modification of behavior through learning which occurs as a result of education instruction development and planned experiences” (Oliseh, 2005). Training tried to change the behavior of the employee in the work place to increase employee’s skills according to standard which exists in the company. The organizations usually implement training when they want to change process of manufacturing or service, training for new skills gives opportunity for better career paths (within the company or in the labor market), higher income and employability.

Manpower training and development has the key role in improving knowledge and skills on human resource in any organization. HR professionals are very important for the organization. Training can bring them at par with the organization's goals and attuned with the industry trends is necessary. The companies should improve continually employee’s skills and attitude by training and manpower development to ensure enforcing optimal performance. As shown in Figure 4, manpower training and development can change and improve the level of ability and attitude of the employees in the workplace.

Figure 4 Input-Process-Output (IPO) of Manpower Training's Model

Also, training and manpower development undoubtedly lead employee to better productivity through improved technical and managerial skills and better morale within the workforce. The creation of a culture of training and manpower development within an organization confirms within the minds of staff that they are worthy part of the construction company.

The culture of an enterprise is one of the hardest aspects to manage; staff training and manpower development have the power to change organizational culture for the better situation in construction company. According to David (2008) “Many managers understand the value of a skilled workforce, many companies fail to realize the benefits that minimal improvements in employee skills by training can make in an organization”.

According to many studies, implementation of training system in company can improve some factors in the company such as performance improvement, increased productivity, increased profit, improved satisfaction of employees, increased employee moral and increased revenue.

As shown in Figure 5, the effectiveness of training and manpower development can improve the job satisfaction, technical skills, enhancement of salary and change the company culture to a proper level that company can compete with other companies as well as owners or contractors or HRM expected. These changes can help to increase and improve profit, productivity and employee's performance in a construction company.

Figure 5 Detailed Relationship Between Training System and Productivity

According to Training Magazine (2004), when senior executives were asked the most important training initiatives, “77% cited aligning learning strategies with business goals; 75% cited ensuring learning content meets the workforce requirements; and 72%, boosting productivity and agility” in the companies. So, most managers know training has had significance for company improvement. Doubtlessly, training and manpower development has important role on series of factors which can nicely enable to increase productivity in the workplace. “The results indicate that employee's training is one of the functions that consistently over the years are perceived as having considerable room for productivity improvement” (Arditi and Mochtar, 2000). The companies need to have a proper system for the implementation of manpower training and development, as using Instructional System Design (ISD) and Instructional Design (ID) in the construction companies that are able to know and design a good instructional system in projects, it is necessary to establish this intellectual education system for companies to get most benefit from training.

Training Needs Assessment in Construction Training

Before the implementation of the training system the managers must be able to know their employee’s needs concerning training. And “training needs are initially identified by reviewing regulatory requirements and existing training programs, and/or conducting a needs analysis” (Yoder,1993).

According to Chang and Chiang (2011) TNA (Training Needs Assessment) is a process of confirming the knowledge and technology necessary for achieving organizational goals, and it is necessary to provide the employees through training, and which training should be provided". This process must continuously effort to find the existing needs of the organization concerning training to achieve organizational development goals. This analysis for training needs is usually included: The three levels are organizational level, operational and individual level.

According to Warshauer (1988), a good TNA provides the following benefits such as: 1) increasing the commitment of the management to enable participants to participate in training and development continuously; 2) increasing the visibility of training functions; 3) elaborating critical organizational issues; 4) making the best use of limited organizational resources; 5) providing training courses and Training design ideas; 6) providing employees with knowledge and skills for performing their duties; 7) helping an organization find the goal of performance, and; 8) improving employee relations and morale.

Training system in any organization and industry must be strictly emphasized to know its aims concerning employees then when the organization could know it by analyzing training needs, so the organization can be able to go to the next level of training system after knowing what its mission is.

Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation and Financial Assessment of the Training System

The design phase conceptualises the project, the phase involves learning objectives, assessment tools, exercises, content, subject matter analysis, learning sequence and media asset selection. Design is an important part of a training manpower development in HR because after analyzing the training needs of employees, the organization must be able to plan a proper system to achieve the aims of the organization. Then the company can realize which way and designed program is an opportunity for employees and target company. According to Yoder (1993) the design of training includes:

1. Self-paced instruction: This is any form of instruction that does not require the presence of an instructor at the training setting. However, feedback must be provided;
2. On-the-job training (OJT): This relates to formal training on the job. A worker becomes experienced on the job over time due to modification of job behavior at the point of training or acquisition of skills;
3. Classroom: training presented to groups of various sizes, typified by stand up lecture, seminar, or group interaction. Classroom instruction works well for presentation of fundamental and basic theoretical knowledge, and;
4. Laboratory/Workshop: training that emphasizes hands on practical experience in a controlled environment.

This step establishes the development of current job descriptions and standards and procedures. Job descriptions should be clear and concise and may serve as a major training tool for the identification of guidelines. Once the job description is completed, a complete list of standards and procedures should be established from each responsibility outlined in the job description. This will standardize the necessary guidelines for any future training. Also, the development phase involves the creation of the learning objects or course based on the completed storyboards. According to Yoder (1993) training methods selected should be based on the objectives and settings for the course, training methods are techniques of communicating instructional material to trainees.

These materials are references, info packs, case studies, movies, games, and other visual aids. This is also a great time to ensure that feedback from previous sessions is included. If the attendees are bored, they will not stay engaged with the facilitator. If attendees are disengaged, they will absorb less knowledge. Keep them engaged with activities such as trivia questions, interactive exercises, and group discussions. It is a proven fact that engagement raises knowledge retention. The developers create and assemble the content assets and the programmers build the functions and integrate the assets, testers complete User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and debugging occurs. Project variations are applied and the release occurs after approval.

The implementation phase involves the development of documentation, user guides and training manuals. The documentation covers the course curriculum, learning outcomes, navigation, assessment and learning tools. This process is one of the important parts of training system and it must be delivered properly to employees.

According to Yoder (1993), activities of implementation are:

1. Conduct training: If specified in the training development and administrative guide, trainees should be pretested to ensure that they are adequately prepared. Trainee performance should be monitored and evaluated during training;
2. Conduct in training evaluation: During training, data should be collected for subsequent use in evaluating and improving training program effectiveness. Evaluation information is collected from test performance data, instructor critiques and trainee critiques, and;
3. Document training: The documentation of training includes preparing, distributing, storing, controlling, and retrieving records and reports that address the training program and trainee participation.

The evaluation of training usually exists through each stage of training system. According to the Model of the Training Process, from first to the last part, this system has satisfied well the organization concerning its needs. An evaluation model for Project Management Training Programs is necessary to administer the training system according to aims of project management for promotion of HR in construction industry, and evaluation must have achieved three main objectives (Sharon, 2009):

- 1) Assess if intended learning and development objectives have been met, and;

2) Continuous improvement of learning and development, and; 3) Assess whether resources are used wisely.

The Evaluation Phase consists of two parts: formative and summative. Formative evaluation is present in each stage of the ISD process. Summative evaluation consists of tests designed for domain specific criterion referenced items and provides opportunities for feedback from the users. All system outputs are a direct reflection of inputs, processes, and adjustments. The training process is no different. If the outputs of the program are less than desired, then changes to the program may be necessary. Companies should establish a systematic evaluation process to enhance the effectiveness of the training (Warshauer, 1988). The evaluation of the program should occur in two phases (Yoder, 1993):

- 1) Immediately after the program, and;
- 2) Some period later (for instance 6 months).

The evaluation performed immediately after the program serves to correct urgent training issues such as incorrect data. This is also the time to concentrate on instructor techniques. The later evaluation determines whether the training enhanced employee and/or company performance. The phases are sequential, with the outputs of the previous phases providing the inputs to those that follow.

Figure 6 depicts the different phases and their relationships, training delivery methods consist of the techniques and materials used by trainers to structure learning

experiences. Rapid prototyping involves the process of receiving continual or formative feedback while instructional materials are being developed. Rapid prototyping develops learning experiences in a continual design-evaluation process, known as the spiral cycle. The iterative approach means that courses are continually improved as the cycle continues (Sharon, 2009).

Figure 6 Model of the Training Process

The organization can assess its training system by some methods such as Kirkpatrick Model and Financial Assessment of training (ROI, ROE).

One of the methods to assess training system is through the Kirkpatrick Model which described a series of articles on training evaluation by Donald Kirkpatrick in the 1960's where he identified four stages of evaluation. Despite its age, Kirkpatrick's model continues to be used in contemporary research which includes:

1) Reaction; 2) Learning; 3) Behavior, and; 4) Results.

Reaction of Kirkpatrick's Model was mostly concerned with the level of the learner's happiness with the learning program" (Rossett and Kendra, 2001). What this stage really needs is to ensure that the performance intervention (learning program) actually conforms to the individual requirements. "If the managers cannot convince employees that they need to learn the new tasks (motivation), then they probably never learn to perform correctly or once they complete the learning program" (Rossett and Kendra, 2001). They will probably not put their newly learned skills and knowledge to full use.

Thus, the individual needs are the foundation of the Four Needs (Rossett and Kendra, 2001) as shown in Figure 7 below:

Figure 7 Kirkpatrick's Model

Financial Assessment is a useful way to assess training system in construction companies and can be used as an instrument to know improvement of productivity indirectly by computing of ROI or other methods of financial assessment. On the other hand, the measurement on investment can give us accurate information such as increases in levels of customer satisfaction, increase in productivity, time saved, improved teamwork and enhanced organization commitment (Sharon, 2009).

2.2 Related Studies

Aspects of Training and Development for Construction Industry in the Philippines

Unfortunately, there were few researches about this issue, and one of the main problem for this study was finding local's researches concerning training and manpower development. According to TESDA (2003) "employers whether private,

government or non-government entities are encountering difficulties in recruiting and retaining skilled workers especially managerial, professional and technical labor”.

But most HR departments of big and medium companies in the Philippines have gone beyond the small office level operations to administer their plans about employees and their investment concerning employee’s training is not enough. But the researches were emphasized in construction, and transport, the poor population has a higher proportion of less educated members than the non poor and they need training for improvement of their skills. “Workers need to be equipped with to be employable and support firms’ competitiveness and productivity, and the role of the education and training system in providing them” (World Bank, 2010). According to (TESDA), in the Philippines exists a lot of training program which offer different methods and manners for companies. Investments in human resources capital development come in the form of formal training and education offered by private and public. In the construction industry, “government institutes are ranked as the main source of external training, followed by private institutes and industry associations; in the service sectors, private institutes are ranked first followed by government institutes and industry associations” (World Bank, 2010).

One of the organizations that can implement and counsel about training for companies in the Philippine is TVET System under TESDA which seeks to develop the full human person. “TESDA has been structured along the systems view of the Philippine Technical Vocational Education” (Miape and Cainglet, 2010).

The training and development of the Filipino workforce for skilled employment is provided mostly by the private TVET institutions and TESDA. TESDA's strategic role is organized around 4 mutually reinforcing and iterative components of the technical vocational education and training cycle. The TVET development cycle revolves around the:

1) support systems; 2) delivery systems; 3) TVET financing and; 4) quality assurance system.

There is an active synergy among these four components" (Miape and Cainglet, 2010). TVET, in the Philippines has tried to make sure the skilled workers and technicians are able to meet international work standards as well as the needs of local enterprises (Syjoco, 2006).

Also, the Enterprise Based Training (EBT) scheme is one of TVET delivery mode. The scheme endeavors to reinforce the adoption of an industry-led manpower development strategy. "This covers on-the-job training in enterprises or places of work. It is comprehensive, systematic and enterprise-led which aims to improve productivity and product quality in the Philippines" (Miape and Cainglet, 2010).

Knowledge workers are key assets of organizations in the Philippines but there are some challenges for companies and business managers on "how to develop and harness their employee's knowledge through training and education strategies" (Sibal, 2004).

The development of employee competencies is done in close partnership between HRD specialists and line managers (TESDA). And also, Sibal (2004) described that HRD can apply different methods which can improve the skills and the knowledge of workers in the organization for increasing quality and productivity in companies in the Philippines. Divina M. (2007) classified different methods of training that can improve knowledge and skills of employee in the Philippines in large companies toward employee’s productivity as shown in Figure 8 below:

Categories of Training
<p>1 Presentation Method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">– Lecture (standard lecture, panel, guest speaker, team teaching, trainee presentation) with use of new technologies such as CD-ROM, Internet and Intranet– Audiovisual techniques (film, video ,slides)
<p>2 Hands-on methods</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">On-the job TrainingStimulationCase studyBusiness gameSelf-directd learningMentoring/CoachingBehavioral modeling
<p>3 Group Building Methods</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">– Team training (team building, cross training group and intergroup encounter)– Action learning (problem solving, task team, project management)– Adventure learning (outdoor training)

Figure 8 Training Methods

The greater utilization of new learning technologies such as the CD-ROM, Internet, and the company intranet/portal in training delivery, storage, and sharing of knowledge are other existing methods throughout the companies for change and building employees' commitment and improvement of skills of employee as well (Divina, 2007). And also, there are some programs for Managers and Directors are offered in the high level of management such as: Job specific, General thinking, General behavior, Computer, Job specific, General thinking, General behavior, Computer, Skilled Production, Job specific, General thinking (World Bank, 2010), for understanding how to increase amount of productivity in the company. According to Leoncio (2000) government training of construction technicians and skilled workers is basically the function of the National Manpower and Youth Council (NMYC) and the Construction Manpower Development Foundation (CMDf) and construction companies can prepare and establish a training system by those organizations in the Philippines to improve productivity and improvement of their performance in workplace. And also DTI as a Philippines organization is offered some courses for The Philippines construction companies. It has claimed that its courses are useful for construction firms and this organization could research and survey on companies where training were implemented by those courses, and after short time they could receive more productivity than before by improvement of manager's skills such as: Construction Project Management; Construction Contract Management; Construction Project Quality Management; Construction Project Cost Management, and; Construction Project Time Management.

Also, the training programs for supervisors is supervisory development courses that geared towards productivity improvement like efficiency and effectiveness in the utilization of project resources like man, money, machines, methods and others.

The Impact of Construction Training and Development on Employee's Performance and Productivity and How to Assess Amount of Productivity

Construction is the world's largest and most challenging industry. Human resource today has a strategic role for productivity increase of any organization, and this makes it superior in the industrial competition, "Productivity is one of the most important factors that affect overall performance of any small or medium or large construction industry" (Gupta, 2012).

Nowadays most construction companies realized the importance of training and its influence on productivity in the construction industry. The importance of training is in the productivity improvement and also reiterated that on the job training program that have brought about an increase in the productivity of construction.

There are many factors that influence construction employee and productivity, this study is focused in all factors which are important on changing productivity concerning the implementation of training. Those factors can be able to change

some elements such as job satisfaction, absenteeism, improvement of performance, wage, change culture of company and etc.

“Improving productivity performance is a primary driver of the UK economic performance and long term sustainable competitiveness” (HM Treasury, 2006). According to Budget Report (2005) “the UK government has developed a strategy for improving productivity and profitability by training and manpower development, innovation and raising UK skills”.

Black and Lynch (2001) used a series of data for 627 US establishments by analyzing this data they found a positive effect of training system on productivity for employees and their companies. The training has an important role in every company and industry such as construction industry to increase their profit and reduction of costs.

Large companies need to have training and manpower development on staff to make them experts. In an HR department led by a Vice President or Director, there might be a training manager, as well as training specialists. This manager collaborates with senior HR executives to determine the role that training plays in the strategic direction of HR and the overall organization. “Training specialists are the ones who conduct classroom training and in house workshops and focus groups” (Mayhew, 2010), all studies had emphasized to establish a training system in organization properly for increasing profit and product.

According to Suganya (2011), tips to improve productivity by training and manpower development includes: 1) making the employees know and properly understand the productivity evaluation methods; 2) providing incentives and appraisals to efficient workers; 3) enhancing discipline measures in the work place; 4) identifying the skills of each employees; 5) giving appropriate feedback to the employees without discouraging them; 6) emphasizing on the positive points to develop productive work, and; 7) providing continuous training to the employees on multidimensional work.

The companies can improve and enhance employee's performance and productivity by providing training and development. Researches indicate that investments in training employees in problem solving, decision-making, teamwork, and interpersonal relations result in beneficial firm level outcomes. This study tried to find different aspects of training and development which had affected employee's performance and company productivity in construction companies.

The Effect of Training, Gender, Absenteeism, Morale and Wage on Job Satisfaction

Most of the literature in this area has focused on the impact of education and training on job satisfaction. Borcharding and Oglesby (1974) investigated the relationship between job satisfaction and construction productivity. Their influence on construction productivity were further determined using data collected through interviews and questionnaires to productivity by increasing employees' satisfaction

likely to be affected by further training (Hee-Sung, 2006). Also, Melanie and Richard (2004) found that training can have an indirect effect on the organization performances and when the job satisfaction increases by efficient training so the company can meet increasing productivity and profitability.

Some researchers showed that there is a difference between training and job satisfaction focusing on gender. “The regressions show a gender difference in the relationship between training and job satisfaction” (Claudia, 2011). This gap is normal because there is a difference between female and male about psychology and learning.

Previous researches revealed that worker absenteeism and low productivity are influenced by the motivation and job satisfaction of workers. Absenteeism is the term generally used to refer to unscheduled employee absences from the workplace. Absenteeism can impose a number of costs on employer such as the lost output of the absent employee. A number of authors have considered the relationship between job satisfaction and absence. Bunch (2007) found that training effectiveness is “relative, but only to the extent that there is no single measure of training success such as productivity or job satisfaction” in the workplace. There are numerous qualitative and quantitative evaluation approaches useful in determining training effectiveness can reduce absenteeism in workplace. “Organizational commitment and job satisfaction is most influential predictor of employee intention to workplace” (Muhammad and Munir, 2013).

A sample of 436 employees working in a large civil service departments was surveyed concerning absence behavior and “they found that the hypothesized interaction between job satisfaction and involvement was significant for both their indicators of absence behavior” (Melanie and Richard, 2004). So by increasing job satisfaction the construction companies can be able to reduce absenteeism behavior of employees. Then, companies are able to prevent delay in the implementation of their projects and increasing costumer's satisfaction and also, increasing profit in the companies.

According to most studies, successful training and education program would create more favorable employee attitudes and loyalty, and help employees in their personal development and advancement. For example, in a study that used 104 employees in five Malaysian public and private organizations that have implemented some training programs; the researcher found out that an organization that practiced some level of teamwork experienced an increase in employees’ organizational attitudes and loyalty and improvement of productivity” (Boon and Arumugam, 2006).

Sozen and Giritli (1996) found that “inadequate training for qualified workforce plus poor communication and attitude greatly affect construction productivity”. It is clear that if the employees had job satisfaction, they would like to perform their duties as well as possible. That is why training is too much important because it can modify employees to acceptable level about morality.

Training is also seen as “a planned process to modify attitude, knowledge or skill behavior through learning experience to achieve effective performance in an activity or range of activities” (Afshan, 2012). This was an effort to index morale based on employee satisfaction. The following factors were constructed to determine employee satisfaction (Nunnally, 2001):

- 1) Mean hours of sick leave taken;
- 2) Ratio of refusals to acceptances to volunteer for overtime with pay;
- 3) Number of grievances filed in a given period;
- 4) Composite scores of job satisfaction;
- 5) Mean performance evaluation scores.

Perceptions of training and its association with organizational commitment are widely researched. Studies described strong positive correlation between training perceptions and organizational commitment. “Organizational commitment and job satisfaction is most influential predictor of employee intention to leave” (Muhammad and Munir, 2013). Improvement of employee’s behavior can indirectly increase the amount of productivity in construction companies.

There was a weight of evidence from the literature relating to the positive wage effects of training. A vast empirical literature has investigated the effects of training using wages as a proxy for productivity. GDP per hour worked can provide a general picture of a company's productivity, that industry training affects the wages of trainees, and the profitability of firms has a way of evaluating the effect on productivity. “We can infer that an industry training qualification is likely to increase

earnings of an individual by between 5% and 20%” (Sharon and Steel, 2004). According to Sharon and Steel, training can affect employee and this effectiveness are able to increase productivity in the company. And this rotary system can continually work for enhancement of productivity in the workplace.

Training is a key element for improved performance because it can increase the level of individual and organizational competency. “It helps to reconcile the gap between what should happen and what is happening between desired targets or standards and actual levels of work performance” (Supangco, 2011). Also, training can be able to change some positive events that help to increase productivity and improvement of performance (Kay, 2007). “Management has to recognize the workforce needs for training and manpower development, through periodical performance appraisal, to avoid performance problems that could be attributed to poorly skilled and trained workforce” (Divina, 2007).

One of the effectiveness of training in the construction is the reduction of the time in projects and so the construction companies can be able to improve on productivity. “The project owners may be responsible for the time overrun when delays, suspensions or interruptions to all or part of the work are caused by an act or failure to act by the owner resulting from breaches of owner’s obligations, stated or implied in the contract” (Oko, 2011).

Training and the Change of Culture of the Company

Definitions of culture is varied but typically include concepts such as shared beliefs, values, and assumptions that are reflected in attitudes and behavior (Kay, 2007). The organization should always prompt the attitudes and behavior of its employees by enforcing training for them and managers of the organization and to put their employee's in an acceptable level concerning attitude by the implementation of training that causes change the on culture of company. "The culture which results in improved labor productivity would include lessons learned and continuous improvement across projects" (Volkman, 2011).

There has been considerable interest in the relationship between organizational culture and variables such as productivity. "There is little recognition of the entrenched values, beliefs, and assumptions that prevent effective training" (Kay, 2007). The idea of integrated training and manpower development becomes relevant as it helps in promoting a spirit of teamwork as well as uplifting knowledge and skills leading to improved productivity. If the organization emphasizes more teamwork and commitment by changing the culture of organization so it may get more productivity. Changing the culture can improve organizational commitment that is further divided into several dimensions (Muhammad and Munir, 2013).

“The concept of teams and teamwork is increasingly important to productivity and employees’ organizational commitment in the workplace” (Kay, 2007). So improvement of commitment can be a main factor to increase productivity in companies, and organization must improve it by training and giving knowledge and experiences to employees properly.

The Impact of Training and Development on Employees and Construction Companies in the Philippines

Construction companies in the Philippines that are a part of ASEAN always try to obtain high level of productivity. “East Asian countries have been growing quite fast over the last decade, even spectacularly so, for the newly industrialized economies (NIEs), mostly driven by labor productivity” (World Bank, 2010).

Training activities have remained the same since 2003 in the Philippines. Indicators such as percentage of payroll cost spent on training, and average training days for management, professional/technical employees, and manual employees have generally increased and then improvement of Productivity (Supangco, 2011). The experiences of the 120 large companies in the Philippines showed “the importance of training and strategy to ensure that its people’s skills are updated” (Divina, 2007). More importantly, “employers in the Philippines, whether in the private sector or in government, believe that an investment in education and

training is the key to raising productivity in the workplace, and should lead to a sustained increase in labor incomes” (TESDA). So most companies in the Philippines have properly used training methods like lecture, video, role plays, or simulations to enhance the creative, productivity, problem solving and people skills of the employees (Divina, 2007).

Other tasks of training are to improve behavior and employee’s skills (technical skills) of employee to get more productivity and profit. “Behavioral training are those that aim to enhance the social-emotional-psychological skills of the employees, while technical training are those training that aim to improve the conceptual and technical skills of the workforce and enable them to effectively and efficiently perform” (Divina, 2007). By behavioral and technical training the employees and specially managers are able to improve their skills and their knowledge and they can understand which ways are useful to manage a company as a construction company. Also, they can be able to design, analyze, change method, how to work with team and what must be their attitude and behavior in an organization, after learning and getting knowledge concerning them.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design of the study which generally describes the methodology being used and its target participants. The detailed methods to sampling, instruments and validation and data gathering from primary and secondary sources are similarly discussed as well as how the researcher intends to statistically treat the gathered data.

3.1 Research Design

In this study, the descriptive and quantitative research method is used. Descriptive research describes and interprets the meaning of data. It is also concerned with the existing conditions, practices, standards, processes, effect factors, or trends that are developing.

The researcher believes that this method is suitable for this study in implementing human resource development in selected construction companies in Metro Manila, Philippines. Using the descriptive survey method, the researcher could describe the factors affecting the human resource development toward increasing employee's performance and productivity for a successful project implementation among construction companies. In addition with the qualification

method, data on each material's quality and quantities of the human resource development on employee's performance and productivity could be evaluated.

This research will evaluate the impact of human resource development on employee's performance and productivity of selected licensed AAA construction companies to find out high-performance and capability outcomes. Comparing the various research method, descriptive research will be adopted. Descriptive research describes and interprets the meaning of data. It is also concerned with the existing condition, practices, standards, processes, effect factors, or trends that are developing.

3.2 Research Locale

The target participants of the questionnaire survey comprised mainly of people who work in the construction site. This group of people was chosen since they are most likely to possess substantial experience and background knowledge on the subject matter in making judgment and opinions that are relevant towards achieving the objectives of the study. The respondents of this study are limited to ten (10) selected construction companies which are classified an (AAA) located in Metro Manila, Philippines. As shown in Table 1. And from each company five (5) persons will be randomly selected to answer the survey questionnaire. Some of them are project managers, engineers, construction managers and other experts.

Table 1 Selected Company Information List

No.	Company name	Address
1	C C T CONSTRUCTORS CORPORATION	3rd Floor Princess Building, 104 Esteban St., Legaspi Village Makati Commercial Ctr., Makati
2	FOUNDATION SPECIALISTS, INC.	4th Flr. Legaspi Towers 200, Paseo de Roxas Legaspi Village, Makati
3	ASIAN CONSTRUCTION & DEVELOPMENT CORP.	2nd Flr., Ajinomoto Bldg., Sen Gil Puyat Ave. Makati
4	C.B. GARAY PHILWIDE BUILDERS	CBG Bldg. #16 Yakal West Street, Pasig City
5	DDT KONSTRACT, INC.	Unit 401 Lancaster Hotel, Shaw Blvd, Mandaluyong
6	D.M. CONSUNJI, INC.	DMCI Plaza Bldg., 2281 Chino Roces Ave. Ext., Pasong Tamo 2000 Up, Ecology Vill., Makati
7	E.C. DE LUNA CONSTRUCTION CORPORATION	58 B St. Francis Shangrila Place, EDSA cor. Ortigas Center, Shaw Boulevard, Mandaluyong
8	E.E. BLACK, LTD.	53 Paseo de Roxas, Urdaneta Village , Makati City
9	URBAN CONSOLIDATED CONTRACTORS PHILS., INC.	10/F Heart Tower Bldg.,108 Valero St., Salcedo Vill. Makati City, Makati
10	AKN CONSTRUCTION CORPORATION	5044 Filmore St., Palanan, Makati City

Respondent Company Information

The research was focused on the selected licensed (AAA) construction companies within Metro Manila only. The researcher randomly chose the ten (10) companies as the respondents. Table 1 shows the respondent companies' information.

3.3 Source of Data and Sample

The purposive sampling method was used in choosing the respondents. The companies that participated in this study have enough experience about HRM in the construction industry. The respondents of this study are limited to ten (10) selected construction companies which are classified as (AAA) located in Metro Manila, Philippines. And from each company five (5) persons will be randomly selected to answer the survey questionnaire. Some of them are project managers, engineers, construction managers and other experts. The purposive sampling method was used in choosing the respondents. The companies that participated in this study have enough experience about HRM in the construction industry.

The use of descriptive method demands the use of statistical procedures to ensure a level of confidence that would result to the validity of the findings of the study. Doing otherwise may get a descriptive study unscientific.

3.3.1 Demographic Profile of Respondents according to Gender

Figure 9 Distribution of Respondents According to Gender

As presented (Figure 9), out of the total (50) respondents thirty six (36) or 72% are Male while fourteen (14) or 28% of the total respondents are Female. The distribution of the respondents by gender is consistent with the distribution of the construction industry professionals in general where males greatly outnumber the number of employees.

3.3.2 Demographic Profile of Respondents according to Civil Status

Figure 10 Distribution of Respondents According to Civil Status

As shown in Figure 10, the grouping consists of four distributions. Out of the total (50) respondents twenty one (21) or 42% are Married, fourteen (14) or 28% are Single, eleven (11) or 22% are Separated, four (4) or 8% are Widowed.

3.3.3 Demographic Profile of Respondents according to Group Age

Figure 11 Distribution of Respondents according to Group Age

Figure 11 shows the profile of the respondents classified according to age. As shown, the grouping consist of five age brackets distribution. Two (2) of the fifty (50) respondents comprising 4% with age bracket from under 20 years, seventeen (17) or 34% within age bracket from 20 – 29, sixteen (16) or 32% within age bracket from 30 – 39, ten (10) or 20% within age bracket from 40 – 49, and also five (5) or 10% within age bracket from 50 or above.

3.3.4 Demographic Profile of Respondents according to Work Experience

Figure 12 Distribution of Respondents according to Work Experience

Figure 12 shows that most of the respondents have at least 5 years experience, with only seven (7) of the respondents or 14% having less than 5 years of work experience in their job. It can be observed from Figure 4.4. that a majority of the respondents have 5 years or between 5 and 8 years of experience (18) or 36%, followed by those having 8 or between 8 and 10 years (9) or 18%, some of them have 3 or between 3 and 5 years of experience (8) or 16%, and just (8) or 16% of the respondents have at least 10 years of experience.

3.3.5 Demographic Profile of Respondents according to Educational Background

Figure 13 Distribution of Respondents according to Educational Background

Figure 13 shows the educational attainment, more than half (27) or 54% of the respondents are college graduates, nine (9) or 18% have master’s degrees, six (6) or 12% have specific certifications, five (5) or 10% of the respondents are Associate holder, and the last just three (3) of the respondents or 6% have Ph.D. degree. Thus, the respondents in this survey are mostly college graduates, with almost half, and 24% of the respondents have post-graduate degrees. Most of the respondents of this study are undergraduates. Moreover, just 22% of the respondents did not study in college, yet served as assistant to managers in their respective companies. Furthermore, it is difficult to finish Master or Ph.D. degrees without enough time and scholarship grant since it is rather expensive.

3.3.6 Demographic Profile of Respondents according to the Type of Employee's Job.

Figure 14 Distribution of Respondents according to the Type of Employee's Job

Figure 14 shows that the biggest number of the respondents are Operational Staffs that is (13) or 26% of the respondents, the number of Executive Managers, HR Directors and others is for each of them (6) or 12% of the respondents. The rest are almost (19) or 38% of the respondents that it distributed among Project Managers, Project Engineers, Superintendents, VPs, and Supervisors.

3.3.7 Demographic Profile of Respondents according to the Current Employment Level.

Figure 15 Distribution of Respondents according to Current Employment Level

Figure 15 shows that of the fifty (50) respondents, twenty (20) or 40% of them belonged to the Executive Level while sixteen (16) or 32% of them belonged to Non-Executive Level, nine (9) or 18% of them are in Senior Management Level and (5) or 10% are classified in others. As shown, majority of the respondents occupied the Executive Level and Non-Executive Level.

3.3.8 Demographic Profile of Respondents according to Training Experience

Figure 16 Distribution of Respondents according to Training Experience

Figure 16 presents the distribution of the respondents in terms of training experience. As presented, twenty four (24) or 48% of the respondents have experienced short-term on-the-job training in their companies, fifteen (15) or 30% of them have experienced moderate-term on the job training, and just eleven (11) or 22% of them have experienced long-term on-the-job training. As shown, majority of the respondents have experienced short and moderate-term of on-the-job training that is equivalent to 78% of them.

3.3.9 Demographic Profile of Respondents according to the Type of Training

Figure 17 Distribution of Respondents according to Type of Training

Figure 17 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of the type of training the respondents have had in their companies. This table shows that on the job training (OJT) has 38 %, next is self-directed learning representing with 21% ranking second, presentation method (Internet and CD) has approximately 18%, and ranking fourth is through Seminar and Conference approximately 14%.

3.4 Instrument for Gathering Data and Validation

In this study, the researcher identified the impact of human resource development on employee's performance and productivity in construction industry. Since the study is focused on the respondents' management ability, the researcher used the interview method to help him gather other information about human resource development process and program plan in construction companies in Metro Manila. The researcher used the survey questionnaire as the primary tool for collecting data. The questionnaires used in this study were presented in the Appendix. In making the questionnaire, the introspection principle was used since it is basically a self-report that provides information of past, present or future conditions that guide respondents of certain population, including evaluation of the impact of human resource development on employee's performance and productivity in selected construction companies in Metro manila.

Using the questionnaire enabled the researcher to collect data faster and cheaper than any other instrument. To clarify the questionnaires interpretation, direct interview on the respondents was carried out. Thus, the interpretation of the data would be accurate and broader.

Furthermore, the other purpose of using questionnaire as a research instrument for survey are as follows: 1) respondents of this research are varied practitioners of construction industry such as project managers, engineers,

construction managers, superintendents and other experts; 2) using questionnaire could make the research work more efficiently, and; 3) using questionnaire could assist the respondent to better understand the questions and explain the question more clearly.

After formulating the objectives of the study and the conceptual framework, the researcher constructed the survey instrument under the close guidance of the adviser. The items in the questionnaire were based on human resource development being used by the managers, engineers, operational staffs and other experts in construction companies in Metro Manila. In this study, the survey questionnaire was divided into three main parts: Part I focuses on the general information about the respondents. The information to be provided by the respondents consists of their current position, age, gender, status, experience, the educational background and others. Part II is focused on the assessment of the level of the respondent's awareness concerning human resource development used in construction industry for the improvement of the employee's performance and productivity without giving them any background about training system. Part III is focused in the identification and determination of the prospects, challenges of human resource development in order to understand the impact of human resource development on employee's performance and productivity from the respondents, and also identification of which methods are efficient to evaluate productivity and employee's performance in selected construction companies in Metro Manila.

The questions asked in the questionnaire are in the form of multiple-choice questions. As mentioned previously, this was done for the convenience of the respondents in order to lessen the time of answering the survey questionnaire and also of aiding the respondents in making decisions without confusing them. However, the use of multiple-choice questions would require the anticipation of a whole range of possible answers which could be given. With this in mind, the options have to be formulated carefully. The questionnaires were personally distributed and retrieved by the researcher to target respondents. Upon the retrieval of the questionnaires the researcher counted, analyzed, and interpreted the data using tables, under the supervision of his adviser and expert in statistics. The completed questionnaires were collected from them. Confidentiality and anonymity of the participants were protected as their names were not required on the questionnaires.

3.5 Procedure for Gathering Data

The researcher sought permission to conduct the study from the construction company's management concerned before making the survey. In the questionnaire, the primary data were obtained directly from all respondents consisting of managers, engineers and other experts. Secondary data were obtained mainly from various information regarding company's profile and history, organization, and employee's description.

The questionnaires were personally distributed and retrieved by the researcher to the respondents's target. Upon the retrieval of the questionnaires, the researcher counted, analyzed, and interpreted the data using tables, under the supervision of the adviser and an expert statistician.

3.6 Statistical for Analyzing Data

The following statistical methods and techniques were planned for a better interpretation of the data gathered.

Importance Index Rate of the Performance

The data for the important factor was calculated using an importance index. These ratings or rate of importance shows the level of each factor. The rate or degrees of the level of the performance measure will be distributed in five categories, with 5 being the highest. The assigned values are based on the level of importance as follows:

- 1. Strongly Disagree 1
- 2. Disagree 2
- 3. Neutral 3
- 4. Agree 4
- 5. Strongly Agree 5

In analyzing the data, the researcher used qualitative and quantitative method in order to determine aspects, challenges and the impact of human resource development toward increasing employee's performance and productivity for managers, engineers and other experts of construction industry in selected construction companies in Metro Manila and effectiveness based on their participation and practices.

Therefore, each factor within the variables was spelled out and expressed by scoring. Every question scored within a variable was calculated. The following is the calculation of the index values obtained of rate importance of their performance factors:

$$\text{Importance index of a factor} = (X1 \times 1 + X2 \times 2 + X3 \times 3 + X4 \times 4 + X5 \times 5) \div N$$

(2)

Where

X1,X2,..... : Represents the frequency of responses in a particular rating;

5,4,3,..... : Represents the numerical score of the respective rating;

N : Number of respondents or the total number of respondents;

With the rating (weighted) scale given as below:

1. Strongly disagree ($1 \leq \text{Average} < 1.50$)
2. Disagree ($1.5 \leq \text{Average} < 2.5$)

- 3. Neutral ($2.5 \leq \text{Average} < 3.5$)
- 4. Agree ($3.5 \leq \text{Average} < 4.5$)
- 5. Strongly agree ($4.5 \leq \text{Average} < 5.0$)

The following formulas were utilized for the statistical analysis of data gathered.

Percentage

This was used as a descriptive measure especially in showing the relationship of parts to a whole. It is solved by using the following formula:

$$\text{Percentage (\%)} = (F \div N) \times 100 \%$$

(3)

Where :

% = Percentage

F = Frequency of responses

N = Total number of respondents

CHAPTER 4

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION OF DATA

In this chapter, the data and information collected from identified research population are presented and analyzed. The statistical tools, as previously described, were utilized to aid the research study in understanding the gathered results. These results will then be used to answer the research question, test the hypothesis, and make a decisive conclusion. Finally, recommendations specific to those who might be concerned with and interested in the topic will be suggested. Specifically, analysis was made to find out the impact of human resource development on employee's performance and productivity in selected construction companies in Metro Manila. This research was focused on identifying and determining the influence of human resource training and organization development which are the two main parts of human resource development.

The researcher, in undertaking the impact of human resource development on employee's performance and productivity in selected construction companies in Metro Manila, considering the following specific questions:

PROBLEM 1 **What is the level of awareness of the respondents concerning human resource development in increasing employee's performance and productivity and company profit in the selected construction companies in Metro Manila as perceived by the respondents?**

The researcher, in answering this problem, used a Survey Questionnaire which is subdivided into eleven specific questions that represent significant areas of concern. *Some questions necessitated the respondents to answer the questions by giving three options of answers as directed in the instructions. Therefore, the total number of response for these kinds of question do not correspond to the exact number of respondents which is 50, but can be more than 50.* The eleven areas are as follows:

1.1 From your experience, what kind of methods of training are considered most efficient and economical for improving skills and behavior of employees in your company?

The researcher looked into the opinions of the respondents as to how they perceived to be the most efficient method of training for improving skills and behaviour of employees. For purposes of clarity and organization, the researcher presents Table 2 below:

Table 2 Opinion of Respondents Concerning the Most Efficient Method of Training to Improve Employee's Skills and Behavior

Methods of Training	Rank
On the job training	1
Self-directed learning	2
Mentoring/Coaching	3
Seminars	4
Conferences	5
Presentation method such as internet , Intranet and (CD-ROM)	6
Others	7

Table 2 shows that most of the respondents believed that on the job training (OJT) is the best way to improve the skills and behavior of employees in the construction companies. Most of the respondents ranked it as their first choice, most reasonable for the respondents to choose it as their number one choice because it is easy and cheap to implement for employees in the workplace. Self-directed learning and Mentoring/Coaching ranked at number two and three respectively. Seminars and Conferences were ranked fourth and fifth choice respectively, followed by presentation method such as internet, Intranet and (CD-ROM) at sixth, and last or the seventh is others.

1.2 *Who are the most responsible officials to develop HRD in construction company?*

The researcher looked into the opinions of the respondents as to who are most responsible officials in a construction company to develop HR. For purposes of clarity and organization, the researcher presents Table 3 below:

Table 3 Opinion of Respondents Concerning Who Have Most Responsibility to Develop HR

Responsible Person in the Development of HR	Rank
HR director	1
President of the company	2
Vice president of the company	3
Contractor	4
Project manager	5
Executive manager	6
Others	7

Table 3 shows that in terms of responsibility, most of the respondents ranked the HR director as their first choice because they believed that the HR director has a direct responsibility in the workplace to expand and develop HR in their companies.

Ranked second is the president of the company who has a high position in the company and, they have the most responsibility in leading the employees.

1.3. What kind of courses are most suitable for you to become more efficient in your company and to improve your knowledge and ability in your construction company?

Table 4 Opinion of Respondents Concerning Most Suitable Courses to Improve Employee’s Knowledge and Ability

Most Suitable Course to Improve One's Knowledge and Ability	Rank
Construction project management	1
Construction project quality management	2
Construction project cost management	3
Construction project material management	4
Construction project time management	5
Others	6
Construction new methods and technology management	7

Table 4 shows that most of the respondents believed that construction project management is the best course to improve the knowledge and ability of the employees in construction companies. Most of the respondents ranked it as their number one choice, construction project quality management and construction project

cost management are ranked at number two and three respectively. Construction project material management and construction project time management are ranked fourth and fifth respectively, followed by others at sixth, and last is construction new methods and technology management.

1.4 *Which of the following items are most important for organizational development (OD) toward the improvement of skills, employee's performance and productivity in the company?*

Table 5 Opinion of Respondents Concerning Factors To Be Most Important for Organizational Development (OD)

Factors Most Important for Organizational Development	Rank
Strategic leadership	1
System analysis and design	2
IT (Information technology)	3
Management of change	4
Creative problem solving and making decision	5
Statistical process control	6

Table 5 shows that most of the respondents ranked the strategic leadership as their first choice for the improvement of organizational development (OD), improving the skills, employee's performance, and productivity in the company.

Ranked second is the system analysis and design. IT (Information technology) and management of change followed at number three and four respectively. Creative problem solving and making decision and statistical process control are ranked fifth and sixth, and last is others.

1.5 Which of the following reasons are most important for establishing the HRD?

Table 6 Opinion of Respondents Concerning Most Important Reasons for Establishing HRD

Reasons for Establishing HRD	Rank
Need to improve the quality of your output	1
New hires did not have necessary skills, ability and behavior	2
Need to improve employee's performance and productivity	3
Need to train more to remain competitive	4
Changes in technology	5
Changes in the organization of work	6
Others	7

Table 6 shows that most of the respondents believed that the need to improve the quality of the output is as most important in establishing HRD in the construction companies. Most of the respondents ranked it as their number one choice, new hires

who expectedly do not have yet necessary skills, ability and behavior ranked number two. Ranked third is the need to improve employee's performance and productivity. The need to train more to remain competitive and the changes in technology are ranked fourth and fifth respectively.

1.6 What kind of assessment are the most efficient for HRD in construction company?

Table 7 Opinion of Respondents Concerning Most Efficient Way to Assess HRD

Most Efficient Way in Assessing the HRD	Rank
Evaluating profit of the company	1
Quality assessment in project	2
Time assessment in project	3
Financial assessment such as Return-on-Investment (ROI)	4
Evaluating employee's skills and behavior	5
Computing expenses of project before and after HRD	6
Others	7

Table 7 shows that most of the respondents ranked the evaluation of the profit of the company as their first choice in assessing the efficiency of HRD in construction

companies. The second is quality assessment in project. Time assessment in project and financial assessment such as Return-on-Investment (ROI) followed at number three and four respectively. Evaluating employee’s skills and behavior and computing expenses of project before and after HRD are ranked fifth and sixth, respectively.

1.7 *What are the benefits of HRD for employees in construction companies?*

Table 8 Opinion of Respondents Concerning Benefits of HRD for Employees

Benefits of HRD to Employees	Rank
Improvement of skills and reduction of error in the workplace	1
Promotion of employee’s level and position in the company	2
Increasing safety and reduction of injury in the workplace	3
Improvement of employee’s satisfaction and employee satisfaction	4
Learning how to work with new methods and ways toward increasing productivity	5
Increasing the salary of employee	6
Others	7

Table 8 shows that most of the respondents believed that improvement of skills and reduction of error in the workplace has the most benefit for employees applied by

HRD in construction companies. Most of the respondents ranked it as their number one choice, the second is promotion of employee’s level and position in the company, increasing safety and reduction of injury in the workplace followed at number three. Improvement of the employee’s satisfaction and employee’s satisfaction was ranked fourth choice.

1.8. *What are the benefits of HRD for construction companies?*

Table 9 Opinion of Respondents Concerning Benefits of HRD of Construction Companies

Benefits of HRD to Construction Companies	Rank
Increasing profit for the company	1
Increasing productivity	2
Competing with other companies	3
Administrating and controlling the projects as well as with employees who improved their knowledge and skills by HRD	4
Getting customer's satisfaction by doing project on time and quality	5
Using new and high method and technology can be possible toward reduction of costs	6
Others	7

Table 9 shows most of the respondents ranked the increasing the profit for company as their first choice because it has most benefit for construction companies by applying HRD. The second is increasing productivity. Competing with other companies follows at number third according response of respondents. Administrating and controlling the projects as well as with employees who improved their knowledge and skills by HRD is as their forth choice.

1.9 *From the following factors, which are most important in increasing productivity through HRD in construction company?*

Table 10 Opinion of Respondents Concerning Factors Which are Most Important to Increase Productivity

Most Important Factors to Increase Productivity	Rank
Improving technical skills and knowledge	1
Improving job satisfaction	2
Improving moral and attitude in the workplace	3
Reduction of costs of the company	4
Changing the company culture	5
Reduction of time in project	6
Others	7

Table 10 shows that most of the respondents ranked improving the technical skills and knowledge as their first choice because it is very important to increase employee's productivity in construction company through HRD. The second is improving job satisfaction. Improving moral and attitude in the workplace and reduction of the costs of company followed at number three and four respectively. Changing the company culture and reduction of time in project are ranked fifth and sixth choice, and last is others.

1.10 From the following items, what items do you think are the most significant in increasing organizational performance in construction companies?

Table 11 Opinion of Respondents Concerning Factors Significant to Increase Organizational Performance (OD)

Most Important Factors to Increase Organizational Performance	Rank
Enhancement of productivity in the company	1
Increasing customer's satisfaction	2
Improving technical skills and knowledge	3
Increasing the assets of construction company	4
Reduction of the costs of company	5
Reduction of time in project	6
Others	7

Table 11 shows that most of the respondents believed that enhancement of the productivity in the company is most significant in increasing the organizational performance in construction companies. Most of the respondents ranked it as their number one choice, increasing customer's satisfaction and improving technical skills and knowledge followed at number three and four respectively. Increasing the assets of construction company is ranked fourth, fifth is the reduction of the costs of the company, followed by reduction of time in project is ranked sixth, and last is others.

1.11 Which of the following priorities are significant for human capital development in HRD?

Table 12 Opinion of Respondents Concerning Priorities Significant for Human Capital Development in HRD

Most Significant for Human Capital Development in HRD	Rank
Leadership	1
Reengineering the human resources function	2
Culture / Strategic awareness	3
Strategic integration	4
Strategic alignment	5
Strategic skills / Competencies	6
Others	7

Table 12 shows that in terms of priorities, the respondents ranked leadership as their first choice because it has directly the biggest role to expand and develop human capital development in HRD. The second is re-engineering the human resources function. Culture/strategic awareness and strategic integration followed at number three and four respectively. Strategic alignment and strategic skills and competencies are ranked fifth and sixth, respectively, and last is others.

PROBLEM 2 What are the prospects and challenges of human resource development on employee's performance and productivity in selected construction companies in Metro Manila?

Initially, the researcher made a partition between variables Performance and Productivity, thus, making a two-fold presentation, first part is Performance, and second part is Productivity. Hence, the researcher, in examining the first part of the research problem created eighteen (18) categories or areas of concern, each category contributing an answer to the main question.

Table 13 shows opinion of respondents concerning the prospects of human resource development. There are fourteen (14) questions in the prepared checklist and the respondents offered their opinion using a Likert Scale, as follows: 5 Strongly Agree, 4 Agree, 3 Neutral, 2 Disagree, and 1 Strongly Disagree.

Category 1: Prospects of HRD

Table 13 Opinion of Respondents Concerning the Prospects of HRD

No.	Question	Frequency Analysis					Average Index	Remarks
		Number of the Respondents						
		1	2	3	4	5		
1	Q1	2	4	7	25	12	3.84	Agree
2	Q2	3	6	5	22	14	3.56	Agree
3	Q3	2	7	3	20	18	3.9	Agree
4	Q4	2	3	7	28	10	3.82	Agree
5	Q5	1	3	2	27	17	4.12	Agree
6	Q6	4	5	10	20	11	3.58	Agree
7	Q7	5	11	6	18	10	3.34	Neutral
8	Q8	6	8	6	12	18	3.56	Agree
9	Q9	10	6	9	9	16	3.3	Neutral
10	Q10	9	2	4	24	11	3.8	Agree
11	Q11	5	3	9	21	12	3.64	Agree
12	Q12	8	4	14	14	10	3.28	Neutral
13	Q13	6	8	4	20	12	3.48	Neutral

14	Q14	3	13	4	11	19	3.6	Agree
	Total	66	83	90	271	190	3.63	Agree

Table 13 shows the main factors on the prospects of HRD. Most of the respondents agreed that it is necessary for employee's awareness of HR policy in the companies (Question1), the mean of important index value is 3.84, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree) can show that is necessary to know about HR policy in the organization. Most of the respondents thought that there is a need for assessing the satisfaction of the employee's training (Question 2), the mean important index value is 3.56, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that all companies need to establish a proper system to assess the satisfaction of employee's training. Regarding the training needs to lead and identify a proper way to increase firm performance (Question 3), the mean important index value is 3.9, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that the companies can increase and improve firm performance by following training needs. In terms of the specific process for organization development (Question 4), the mean important index value is 3.82, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that most often companies followed the specific process for OD. Regarding the training needs to identify a useful business strategy (Question 5), the mean important index value is 4.12, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means HRD can find a proper way and strategy to improve business performance. Regarding engagement of training and OD in organization by top managers (Question 6), the mean important index value is 3.58, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that most often top managers followed

HRD in their companies as one of many ways to improve the performance of the organization.

In terms of existing formal training for new employees (Question 7), the mean important index value is 3.34 and close to a rate of 3 (Neutral). This means the awareness of the respondents is uncertain about the training for new employees. Regarding the encouragement of employees for any kind of the training (Question 8), the mean important index value is 3.56, and close to rate 4 (Agree). This means the managers often follow and enforce training methods to improve employee's ability.

In terms of the feedback for HRD by top management (Question 9), the mean of important index value is 3.3, and close to a rate of 3 (Neutral). This means that it is not clear the management of the companies follow a proper feedback through HRD in the organization. In terms of benefits HRD to employees and the companies (Question 10), the mean important index value is 3.8, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that HRD is surely useful for both the company and employee. Regarding the attachment of employees' feeling with team by HRD (Question 11), the mean important index value is 3.64, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means HRD can help employee's performance to be coordinated with team in the workplace. In terms of the influence of HRD to the employee's desire for staying in their companies (Question 12), the mean important index value is 3.28, and close to a rate of 3 (Neutral). This means that respondents do not clearly know about the influence of HRD to the employee's desire for staying in their companies. Regarding the

promotion of the employee's level (Question 13), the mean important index value is 3.48 and also close to a rate of 3 (Neutral). This means that the respondents do not clearly know about the influence of HRD to promote employee's level and position in their companies. Regarding reduction the completion of time and cost of performing projects HRD (Question 14), the mean important index value is 3.6, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that HRD has important role for reduction the completion of time and cost in construction industry.

In summary, about (66) or 9.4% and (83) or 11.9% of the response of the respondents are classified as Strongly Disagree and Disagree, respectively, concerning the prospects of HRD on construction companies; about (90) or 12.9% of the response of the respondents are Neutral and they have uncertain opinion. Finally, most of the respondents answered Agree and Strongly Agree, (271) or 38.7% and (190) or 27.1% of the response of the respondents are Agree and Strongly Agree respectively, the total mean important index value for prospects of HRD is 3.63 and also close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that most of the respondents or 65.8% of them chose agree and strongly agree on the prospects of HRD on construction and its benefits for improving this industry and just 21.3% of them chose Strongly Disagree and Disagree.

Category 2: The Challenges of Implementation of HRD in Construction Company

Table 14 shows opinion of respondents concerning the challenges of HRD implementation in construction companies. There are eight (8) questions in the

prepared checklist and the respondents offered their opinion using a Likert Scale, as follows: 5 Strongly Agree, 4 Agree, 3 Neutral, 2 Disagree and 1 Strongly Disagree.

Table 14 Opinion of Respondents Concerning the Challenges of HRD

No.	Question	Frequency Analysis					Average Index	Remarks	Rank
		Number of the Respondents							
		1	2	3	4	5			
1	Q1	6	3	6	19	16	3.72	Agree	3
2	Q2	4	10	4	14	18	3.64	Agree	4
3	Q3	3	4	5	11	27	4.1	Agree	1
4	Q4	9	10	7	9	15	3.22	Neutral	6
5	Q5	7	5	2	14	22	3.78	Agree	2
6	Q6	14	6	3	15	12	3.1	Neutral	7
7	Q7	9	6	5	16	14	3.4	Neutral	5
8	Q8	13	5	8	6	18	3.22	Neutral	6
	Total	65	49	40	104	142	3.52	Agree	

Table 14 shows the main factors which may cause the challenges on human resource development in construction companies. The data collected shows that most

respondents ranked time as a big problem for implementing training (Question 3), the mean important index value is 4.1, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree) as their first choice. In fact, it is the first problem for the implementation of HRD in the construction company. The second is the number of the employees who need to have training (Question 5), the mean important index value is 3.78, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree) and it is the second problem that identified the implementation of HRD in the construction companies. In terms of the cost of the implementation of HRD (Question 1), and finding a proper training system and OD (Question 2), the means important index value are 3.72 and 3.64 respectively, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree) follow at number three and four. Regarding suitable feedback to control and lead the HRD (Question 7), the mean important index value is 3.4, and close to a rate of 3 (Neutral) is ranked as the fifth problem. This means that respondents believed that the feedback may be one of the problems in implementing HRD in construction companies. Finally, employee's motivation (Question 4) and identifying a proper OD strategy for HRD (Question 8) are both ranked sixth problem and with a mean important index value of 3.22, and close to a rate of 3 (Neutral). Regarding the finding suitable OD strategy and trainers (Question 6) is seventh problem, with a mean important index value of 3.1, and close to a rate of 3 (Neutral).

From the collected data, time, number of the employees, cost, and suitable HRD are classified as main challenges in implementing HRD in the construction companies. But there is no clear answer on how to realize the feedback, employee's

motivation, and OD strategy as problems in the implementation of HRD. The responses of the respondents for these factors are Neutral.

In summary, about 65 or (16.3%) and 49 or (12.2%) of the responses were Strongly Disagree and Disagree, respectively, concerning the challenges of HRD in construction companies; about 40 or (10%) of them chose Neutral and they have uncertain opinion about this issue. Generally, most of the responses of the respondents or 104 or (26%) and 142 or (35.5%) of them posted Agree and Strongly Agree, respectively. The total of means important index value on the prospects of HRD is 3.52 and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that most of the respondents answered Agree and Strongly Agree (61.5%) and these factors are main challenges in the implementation of HRD in construction companies, and just (28.5%) of them chose Strongly Disagree and Disagree as their responses.

Category 3: The Impact of HRD on Employee's Performance and Productivity (Organizational Performance) in Construction Company

Initially, the researcher made a partition between variables Performance and Productivity, thus presenting a two-fold presentation:

The Impact of Human Resource Development on Employee's Performance

This section expressed the opinion of the respondents concerning the impact of HRD on employees' performance and productivity in construction companies. There are seven (7) sub-categories, namely: Planning, Team Work Communication,

Organization, Improvement of Knowledge, Decision Making, Leadership, and Work Process and Results. A checklist of questions are used for each sub-category and respondents offered their opinion using a Likert Scale, as follows: 5 Strongly Agree, 4 Agree, 3 Neutral, 2 Disagree and 1 Strongly Disagree.

Planning

The findings on the opinion of respondents concerning the human resource development on planning in construction company are summarized in Table 15.

Table 15 Opinion of Respondents Concerning HRD on Planning

No.	Question	Frequency Analysis					Average Index	Remarks
		No. of the Respondents						
		1	2	3	4	5		
1	Q1	13	6	10	10	11	3	Neutral
2	Q2	8	4	3	16	19	3.68	Agree
3	Q3	5	5	7	12	21	3.78	Agree
4	Q4	3	4	11	19	13	3.7	Agree

Table 15 shows factors which may be changed by HRD on planning in the organization. Most of the respondents answered Neutral that HRD sets verifiable short and long-term goal (Question 1), the mean important index value is 3, and close to a rate of 3 (Neutral). Most of the respondents think that HRD often helps

employee's goal and the company needs (Question 2), the mean important index value is 3.68, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means all companies that have HRD can offer good expectations from the company and for the employees. Regarding the reflecting employee's goal on the company goal (Question 3), the mean important index value is 3.78, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means employee's goal often follows the goal of the company by improving HRD. In terms of the achievement of employee's expectations (Question 4), the mean important index value is 3.7, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means the employees are able to achieve their goal with the implementation of HRD in the organization.

Team Work Communication

The findings on the opinion of respondents concerning the human resource development on team work communication in construction company are summarized in Table 16.

Table 16 Opinion of Respondents Concerning HRD on Team Work Communication

No.	Question	Frequency Analysis					Average Index	Remarks
		Number of the Respondents						
		1	2	3	4	5		
5	Q5	8	3	2	17	20	3.76	Agree
6	Q6	7	8	4	16	15	3.48	Neutral
7	Q7	6	9	6	20	9	3.34	Neutral

The opinion of the respondents regarding the effectiveness of HRD on team work communication is presented in Table 16 Employee's commitment in the organization by HRD (Question 5), the mean important index value is 3.75, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that implementation of HRD can improve employee's commitment in the workplace. Regarding the improvement of employee's communication skill (Question 6), the mean of important index value is 3.48, and close to a rate of 3 (Neutral). This means that there is uncertain relationship between HRD and the improvement of employee's communication skill. Lastly, improving the interaction of employee with the environment (Question 7), the mean important index value is 3.34 and close to a rate of 3 (Neutral). This means that there is uncertain relationship between HRD and the interaction of employees with the environment.

Organization

The findings on the opinion of the respondents concerning the human resource development on the organization in construction company are summarized in Table 17.

Table 17 Opinion of Respondents Concerning HRD on Organization

No.	Question	Frequency Analysis					Average Index	Remarks
		Number of the Respondents						
		1	2	3	4	5		
8	Q8	8	6	10	12	14	3.36	Neutral
9	Q9	7	6	4	14	19	3.64	Agree
10	Q10	4	3	14	17	12	3.6	Agree
11	Q11	3	1	8	21	17	3.96	Agree

Table 17 shows opinions of respondents concerning HRD on the organization. In terms of frequency of OJT toward enhancement of employee's performance (Question 8), the mean important index value is 3.36 and close to a rate of 3 (Neutral). This means that it is not clear whether OJT improves employee's performance in the workplace. In terms of recruitment and selection process through HRD (Question 9), the mean important index value is 3.64 and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that most respondents believe that there is a meaningful relationship between the recruitment and HRD in the companies. Regarding the improvement of employee's knowledge and performance in case of emergency (Question 10), the mean important index value is 3.6, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that OD through HRD are often useful to improve employee's knowledge

and performance in case of emergency. In terms of the making inspiration to employee for improving performance (Question 11), the mean important index value is 3.96 and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that HRD can inspire employees in doing their jobs.

Improvement of Knowledge, Skills and Attitude

The findings on the opinion of the respondents concerning the human resource development on the improvement of knowledge, skills and attitude in the construction companies are summarized in Table 18.

Table 18 Opinion of Respondents Concerning HRD on Improvement of Knowledge, Skills and Attitude

No.	Question	Frequency Analysis					Average Index	Remarks
		Number of the Respondents						
		1	2	3	4	5		
12	Q12	14	6	1	23	16	3.82	Agree
13	Q13	2	5	10	22	11	3.58	Agree
14	Q14	5	2	8	17	18	3.94	Agree
15	Q15	1	7	5	15	22	4	Agree
16	Q16	6	5	2	19	18	3.76	Agree
17	Q17	8	5	15	12	10	3.22	Neutral

Table 18 shows varying opinions of the respondents on the role of HRD on the improvement of knowledge, skills and attitude. In terms of the improvement of HR outcomes by HRD (Question 12), the mean important index value is 3.82, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that most of the respondents think HRD is a good way to improve HR outcomes in the companies. Regarding the improvement of employee's attitude and behavior (Question 13), the mean important index value is 3.58 and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that most of the respondents believed that HRD helps in changing the attitude and behavior of employees that will improve the situation of the companies.

Regarding the impact of HRD on the skills and experiences of employees (Question 14), the mean important index value is 3.94, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that HRD has important role to improve the skills and experiences of employees in the construction industry.

In terms of the relationship between facts and draw appropriate quickly (Question 15), the mean important index value is 4 (Agree). This means that the staffs can do quickly their jobs through HRD. Regarding the absence of superiors (Question 16), the mean important index value is 3.76, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means employees can do their jobs well even without being monitored by superiors. In terms of making suggestions by employees through HRD (Question 17), the mean important index value is 3.22 and also to a rate of 3 (Neutral). This means that most

of the respondents do not believe there is a certain relationship between HRD and making suggestions by employees.

Decision Making

The findings on the opinion of the respondents concerning the human resource development on decision making in construction company are summarized in Table 19.

Table 19 Opinion of Respondents Concerning HRD on Decision Making

No.	Question	Frequency Analysis					Average Index	Remarks
		Number of the Respondents						
		1	2	3	4	5		
18	Q18	2	3	9	22	14	3.86	Agree
19	Q19	3	5	7	14	21	3.9	Agree
20	Q20	1	9	8	17	15	3.72	Agree
21	Q21	6	4	4	22	14	3.68	Agree

The opinion of the respondents regarding the effectiveness of HRD on decision making is presented in Table 19 Regarding the improvement of the manager's decision making (Question 18), the mean important index value is 3.86, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that the implementation of HRD helps in improving the manager's decision making in the workplace. Regarding the recognition of priorities

in case of emergency (Question 19), the mean important index value is 3.9, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that most of the respondents believe that HRD can help employees to recognizing their priorities in case of emergency through HRD in the workplace. In terms of improving employee's performance by making decision through HRD (Question 20), the mean important index value is 3.72, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that HRD can teach the employees on how to make decisions properly.

Lastly, regarding decision making, accurately in the organization (Question 21), the mean important index value is 3.68, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that the respondents believed that HRD can be able to lead the employees to get knowledge and ability to think and make decisions accurately and with minimum error in the workplace.

Leadership

The findings on the opinion of the respondents concerning the human resource development on leadership in construction company are summarized in Table 20.

Table 20 Opinion of Respondents Concerning HRD on Leadership

No.	Question	Frequency Analysis					Average Index	Remarks
		Number of the Respondents						
		1	2	3	4	5		
22	Q22	4	3	3	21	19	3.96	Agree
23	Q23	7	4	3	15	21	3.78	Agree
24	Q24	3	6	5	26	10	3.68	Agree
25	Q25	5	7	2	19	17	3.72	Agree

Table 20 shows the role of HRD to improve the knowledge, skills, and attitude. In terms of the controlling and monitoring the employees by HRD in the organization (Question 22), the mean important index value is 3.96, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that respondents think HRD is a good way to promote in controlling the projects. Regarding the obedience of employees to their bosses (Question 23), the mean important index value is 3.78, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that most of the respondents believed that HRD promote the methods of management in the workplace toward improving the attitude, and behavior of employees.

In terms of the relationship between employees and leadership (Question 24), the mean important index value is 3.68 and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means

that the implementation of HRD can improve the relationship between employees and leadership in the workplace through HRD. Finally, regarding the reaction of the managers with unexpected development in HR (Question 25), the mean important index value is 3.72, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that most of the respondents believed that HRD can teach managers on how to deal and do smoothly with unexpected conditions and problems in their organization.

Work Processes and Results

The findings on the opinion of the respondents concerning the human resource development on the work processes and results in construction companies are summarized in Table 21.

Table 21 Opinion of Respondents Concerning HRD on the Work Processes and Results

No.	Question	Frequency Analysis					Average Index	Remarks
		Number of the Respondents						
		1	2	3	4	5		
26	Q26	6	5	12	14	13	3.46	Neutral
27	Q27	5	4	8	14	19	3.76	Agree
28	Q28	1	9	5	13	22	3.92	Agree

The opinion of the respondents regarding effectiveness of human resource development on the work processes and results are presented in Table 21.

Regarding the reduction of the failures and errors (Question 26), the mean important index value is 3.46 and close to a rate of 3 (Neutral). This means that the implementation of HRD may be able to reduce employee's failures and errors in the workplace.

In terms of speed of the employee's performance (Question 27), the mean important index value is 3.76, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that the respondents believed that the companies through HRD are able to reduce time of the completion of their projects. Lastly, in terms of the quality of employee's performance (Question 28), the mean important index value is 3.92, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that there is a meaningful relationship between HRD and the quality of employee's performance in the workplace.

Summary of Opinion of Respondents Concerning the Impact of HRD on Employee's Performance

Table 22 Summary of Opinion of Respondents Concerning the Impact of HRD on Employee's Performance

No.	Question	Frequency Analysis					Average Index	Remarks	Rank
		Number of Responses							
		1	2	3	4	5			
1	Planning	29	19	31	57	64	3.54	Agree	5
2	Team Work Communication	21	20	12	53	44	3.53	Agree	6
3	Organization	22	16	36	64	62	3.64	Agree	4
4	Improvement of Knowledge, Skills	26	30	41	108	95	3.72	Agree	2
5	Decision Making	12	21	28	75	64	3.79	Agree	1
6	Leadership	19	20	13	81	67	3.79	Agree	1
7	Work Processes	12	18	25	41	54	3.71	Agree	3
	Total	141	144	186	479	450	3.67	Agree	

It can be seen from Table 22 the summary of the opinion of the respondents concerning the impact of HRD on employee's performance in the construction company.

From the data collected, most of the respondents ranked leadership and decision-making as their first choice, the total means important index value is 3.79, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). It can be shown that leadership and making decision are the most important factors in improving employee's performance through HRD in the construction company.

Ranked second is the improvement of knowledge and skills, the total mean important index value is 3.72, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree) and is found to be important and effective in improving employee's performance through HRD. In terms of work processes and results, the total means important index value is 3.71, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). In terms of the organization, the total means important index value is 3.64, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree).

Ranked fourth is improving employee's performance by implementing. Regarding the effectiveness of HRD on planning in the workplace, the total means important index value of 3.54, and close to a rate of 4 (Neutral), which is ranked fifth. This means that the respondents believe planning is one of the main important factors that must be implemented in the construction companies. Finally, the last factor or the sixth is team work communication, with a mean important index value of 3.53, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree).

In summary, about 141 or (10%) and 144 or (10.3%) of the responses were Strongly Disagree and Disagree, respectively, about the impacts of HRD on

employee's performance, about 186 or (13.3%) of them were neutral and they have uncertain opinion.

Generally, most of the responses or 479 or (34.2%) and 450 or (32.1%) of them posted Agree and Strongly Agree, respectively, the total mean important index value for all factors, which has an impact on employee's performance is 3.67 and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). Most of the responses were marks of Agree and Strongly Agree (66.3%) which means that these factors are the main factors in improving employee's performance by HRD in the workplace.

The Impact of Human Resource Development on Productivity

This section includes four (4) categories, namely: 1) Employee's Satisfaction, 2) Workplace Performance, 3) Employee's Wage and 4) Change of Culture.

Employee's Satisfaction

The findings on the opinion of respondents concerning the impact of HRD on employee's satisfaction in construction company are summarized in Table 23.

Table 23 Opinion of Respondents Concerning HRD on Employee's Satisfaction

No.	Question	Frequency Analysis					Average Index	Remarks
		Number of the Respondents						
		1	2	3	4	5		
1	Q1	8	6	4	13	19	3.58	Agree
2	Q2	7	5	10	16	12	3.42	Agree
3	Q3	8	6	2	18	16	3.56	Agree
4	Q4	9	4	1	15	21	3.7	Agree
5	Q5	6	2	7	17	18	3.78	Agree
6	Q6	2	5	10	15	18	3.84	Agree

Table 23 shows the factors concerning employee's satisfaction. Most of the respondents answered Agree, that improvement of employee's satisfaction can be caused by the improvement of the knowledge and skills through HRD (Question 1), the mean important index value is 3.58, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). Most of the respondents thought that OD helps to improve employee's satisfaction (Question 2), the mean important index value is 3.42, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that all companies by OD through HRD can give more satisfaction to the employees.

Regarding the satisfaction which can be caused by the opportunities in the work from employee's skills and experience (Question 3), the mean important index value is 3.56, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that employee can have more satisfaction with the improvement of the skills and experience through the implementation of HRD. In terms of increasing the pleasure of employee to work by HRD (Question 4), the mean important index value is 3.7, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means the employees are able to have more enjoyable time in the workplace by implementing HRD in the organization.

Regarding reduction of absenteeism in the workplace by HRD (Question 5), the mean important index value is 3.78, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that HRD gives more satisfaction to employees for staying in their workplace. Regarding HRD on the improvement of employee's moral (Question 6), the mean important index value is 3.84, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that most of the respondents believe that there is certain relationship between HRD and the improvement of employee's moral and attitude.

Workplace Performance

The findings on the opinion of the respondents concerning the HRD on workplace performance in construction company are summarized in Table 24.

Table 24 Opinion of Respondents Concerning HRD on Workplace Performance

No.	Question	Frequency Analysis					Average Index	Remarks
		Number of the Respondents						
		1	2	3	4	5		
7	Q7	8	3	6	11	22	3.72	Agree
8	Q8	4	5	12	18	11	3.54	Agree
9	Q9	5	1	18	12	14	3.58	Agree
10	Q10	7	3	5	19	16	3.68	Agree
11	Q11	6	8	4	12	20	3.64	Agree
12	Q12	8	6	7	10	19	3.52	Agree
13	Q13	7	4	6	10	23	3.76	Agree

Table 24 shows the factors which can change the workplace performance through HRD. In terms of the improvement of the organization performance through HRD (Question 7), the mean important index value is 3.72, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that there is a good relationship between HRD and the organization performance. In terms of the reduction the time of completion of the projects through HRD (Question 8), the mean important index value is 3.54, and

close to a rate of 4 (Agree). It is clear that HRD was able to reduce the time of completion of the projects according to the response of the respondents. In terms of the HRD on increasing quality in the workplace (Question 9), the mean important index value is 3.58, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that most of the respondents believed that there is a meaningful relationship between increasing quality and HRD in the companies.

Regarding the increase of ratio output to input in the workplace through the implementation of HRD (Question 10), the mean important index value is 3.68, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that HRD are usually able to increase the ratio output to input in the workplace. In terms of the reduction of the employee's turnover by HRD (Question 11), the mean important index value is 3.64, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that HRD can do some positive things toward the reduction of the employee's turnover for the companies.

In terms of the increase of the client's satisfaction by HRD (Question 12), the mean important index value is 3.52, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that most of the respondents think HRD is a good way to improve the client's satisfaction in the companies. Regarding the improvement of profitability on the company by HRD (Question 13), the mean important index value is 3.76, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that most of the respondents believed that HRD helps in increasing the profitability in the workplace.

Employee's Wage

The findings on the opinion of the respondents concerning the HRD on employee's wage in construction company are summarized in Table 25.

Table 25 Opinion of Respondents Concerning HRD on Employee's Wage

No.	Question	Frequency Analysis					Average Index	Remarks
		Number of the Respondents						
		1	2	3	4	5		
14	Q14	1	8	5	11	25	4.02	Agree
15	Q15	5	1	9	18	17	3.82	Agree
16	Q16	8	8	2	13	19	3.54	Agree

Table 25 shows the role of HRD on employee's wage. Regarding influence of HRD on employee's wage in the construction companies (Question 14), the mean important index value is 4.02, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that HRD has important role in increasing the wage of employees in construction companies. In terms of increasing profit for construction companies (Question 15), the mean important index value is 3.82, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that most of the respondents thought that HRD can increase the profit in the companies. Regarding the wage as a proxy for productivity in the companies (Question 16), the mean important index value is 3.54, and close to rate 4 (Agree). This means that most

of the respondents thought that employee's wage is a proxy and a good indicator to show the improvement of productivity through HRD.

Change of Culture

The findings on the opinion of the respondents concerning the role of HRD on the change of culture in construction company are summarized in Table 26.

Table 26 Opinion of Respondents Concerning HRD on the Change of Culture

No.	Question	Frequency Analysis					Average Index	Remarks
		Number of the Respondents						
		1	2	3	4	5		
17	Q17	8	3	13	11	15	3.44	Neutral
18	Q18	6	7	4	21	12	3.52	Agree
19	Q19	2	2	9	19	18	3.98	Agree

The opinion of the respondents regarding the role of HRD on the change of culture in the organization are presented in Table 26. In terms of the influence of change of culture to use new methods and technology through HRD (Question 17), the mean important index value is 3.44, and close to a rate of 3 (Neutral). This means that most of the respondents believe there is an uncertain relationship between the change of culture in the organization through HRD and new methods and technology toward increasing productivity. In terms of the increase of loyalty of employees in the

organization by HRD (Question 18), the mean important index value is 3.52, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that implementation of HRD can help the increase of loyalty in the workplace. Regarding the possessing of a strong sense of belonging in the company (Question 19), the mean important index value is 3.98, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that most of the respondents believed that HRD can help employees in having a good sense for being and doing their duties.

Summary of Opinion of Respondents Concerning the Impact of HRD on Productivity

Table 27 Impact of HRD on Productivity

No.	Question	Frequency Analysis					Average Index	Remarks	Rank
		Number of Responses							
		1	2	3	4	5			
1	Employee's satisfaction	40	28	34	94	104	3.65	Agree	2
2	Workplace performance	45	30	58	92	125	3.63	Agree	3
3	Employee's wage	14	17	16	42	61	3.79	Agree	1
4	Change of culture	16	12	26	51	45	3.65	Agree	2
	Total	115	87	134	279	335	3.62	Agree	

Table 27 shows the summary of the opinion of the respondents concerning the impact of HRD on productivity in construction company. From the data collected, most of the respondents ranked the employee's wage, the total means important index value is 3.79, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). Employee's wage ranked one of the most important factors in increasing productivity through the implementation of HRD in the construction company. The second is change of culture and the improvement of employees' satisfaction, the total mean important index value is 3.65, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree) and ranked as second choice.

In terms of the workplace performance which ranked number three, the total mean important index value is 3.63, and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). This means that implementing HRD on the workplace will improve performance, which could result to increase productivity in the organization. In summary, about (115) or 12.1% and (87) or 9.2% of the responses of the respondents marked Strongly Disagree and Disagree, respectively, on the impacts of HRD on productivity, about (134) or 14.1% of them are neutral and with uncertain opinion.

Generally, most of the respondents or (279) or 29.4% and (335) or 35.3% of them chose Agree and Strongly Agree, respectively. The total mean important index value for all factors which have an influence on employee's performance is 3.67 and close to a rate of 4 (Agree). Generally, most of the respondents chose Agree and Strongly Agree or 64.7% believed that these factors are important factors in increasing productivity through the implementation of HRD in the workplace.

PROBLEM 3 What are the efficient methods for evaluating employee's performance and productivity to analyze and understand the influences of human resource development in the construction industry?

Initially, the researcher cites the rate of change on employee's performance and productivity through the implementation of HRD in construction companies. It can be noted that as earlier discussed and presented in Table 28 and 29 and Figure 18 and 19.

The Rate of Changes on Employee's Performance and Behavior through the Implementation of Human Resource Development

Most of the respondents about (22) or 44% believed that the implementation of HRD can improve employee's skills and ability 11-15% through implementing HRD, (14) or 28% of the respondents rated it about 6-10% in improving employee's skills and ability, 12 or (24%) of them believed that employee's skills and ability can be improved more than 15%, and (2) or 4% of them believed that the improvement of employee's skills and ability can be about 0-5%.

Hence, the researcher presents this section which discusses the rate of change on employee's performance and capability to show how many percent increase of employee's skills, employee's behavior and employee's performance can be improved by implementing HRD in the workplace.

Table 28 Opinion of Respondents Concerning the Rate of Change on Employee's Performance

No.	Question	Rate of Change on Employee's Performance			
		0 -5%	6 -10%	11-15%	More than15%
1	What is the percentage improvement on employee's skills and ability after developing human resource in your company?	2	14	22	12
2	What is the percentage improvement on employee's behavior and attitude after establishing HRD in your company?	5	18	17	10
3	What is the percentage improvement on employee's performance after training and development in your company?	4	11	19	16

As shown in Table 28 and Figure 18 concerning opinion of the respondents on the improvement of employee's behavior and attitude that shows most of them about (18) or 36% believed that HRD change it about 6-10%, the second is (17) or 34% of them believed that the change in employee's behavior and attitude is about 11-15%, (10) or 20% of them believed this change can be more than 15%, and finally, least (5) or 10% of the respondents believed improvement on the employee's behavior and attitude can be about 0-5%.

Most of the respondents, about (19) or 38%, believed that the implementation of HRD can improve employee's performance between 11 and 15% by implementing HRD, (16) or 32% of the respondents chose more than 15% is the improvement on employee's performance, (11) or 22% of the respondents believed that improvement is about 6-10%, 4 or (8%) of them believed that improvement of employee's performance can be about 0-5% through HRD.

Below is a chart that illustrates the distribution of the respondents according to the percentage of improvement of employee's skills and behavior after implementation of the HRD.

Percentage of the Improvement on the Main Employee's Factors (%)

Figure 18 Distribution of the Respondents According to Percentage of the Improvement on Employee's Skills and Behavior

The Rate of Changes of Organizational Performance and Productivity through the Implementation of Human Resource Development

This section discusses about the rate of changes on the organizational performance and productivity and, it can show how many percent is the improvement of employee's satisfaction, employee's wage, reduction on project's completion time and productivity can be improved through HRD in the workplace.

Table 29 and Figure 19 shows that most of the respondents about (17) or 34% of them believed that the implementation of HRD can improve employee's satisfaction about 11-15% through HRD, (14) or 28% of the respondents believed HRD can improve employee's satisfaction more than 15%, (12) or 24% of the respondents believed that the improvement of employee's satisfaction is about 6-10% (7) or 14% of them believed that the improvement of employee's satisfaction can change about 0-5% through HRD.

The findings on the opinion of the respondents on the increase of employee's wage shows most of them about (20) or 40% believed that HRD can change it about 1-15%, the second is (19) or 38% of them rated that the change in employee's wage is more than 15% , (8) or 16% of them believed that this change can be between 6-10% and, (3) or 6% of the respondents rated that the increase on employee's wage is about 0-5% through HRD.

Table 28 and Figure 19 shows that most of the respondents (18) or 36% of them believed that the implementation of HRD can reduce project's completion time about 11-15% through HRD, (14) or 28% of the respondents rated about 6-10% reduction on project's completion time, (12) or 24% believed that it can be more than 15% and (6) or 12% of them believed that it is about 0-5%. Most of the respondents about (18) or 36% believed that the implementation of HRD can increase productivity about 11-15% by implementing HRD, (15) or 30% rated it about 6-0% for increasing

productivity, (11) or 22% believe this range about 0-5% and (6) or 12% believed that it is more than 15%.

Table 29 Opinion of Respondents Concerning the Rate of Changes on Organizational Performance and Productivity

No.	Question	Rate of Changes on Organizational Performance and Productivity			
		0 -5%	6 -10%	11-15%	More than15%
4	What is the percentage of improving employee's satisfaction after developing human resource in your company?	7	12	17	14
5	What is the percentage of increasing employee's wage after developing human resource in your company?	3	8	20	19
6	What is the percentage of reduction on project's completion time after developing human resource in your company?	6	14	18	12
7	What is the percentage of increasing productivity in the organization after developing human resource in your company?	11	15	18	6

Percentage of the Improvement on the Main Productivity Factors (%)

Figure 19 Distribution of the Respondents According to Percentage of the Improvement on Employee's Satisfaction, Increasing Employee's Wage, Reduction on Project's Completion Time and Increasing Productivity

Determination of the Efficient Methods to Measure Employee's Performance and Productivity in Construction Industry

Efficient Methods for Evaluating Employee's Performance in Construction Company

Table 30 Opinion of Respondents Concerning Efficient Methods for Evaluating Employee's Performance

Efficient Methods for Evaluating Employee's Performance	Rank
The assessment of quality of employee's performance and amount error of employee in the workplace	1
Using 360-degree feedback that depends on what you are measuring of employee's performance	2
Feedback of employee's performance become timely and specifically	3
The assessment of timeliness and cost-effectiveness of projects	4
Self-Assessment	5

Table 30 shows that most of the respondents believed that the assessment of the quality of employee's performance and amount of error of employee in the workplace is the best method for evaluating employee's performance in construction company. Most of the respondents ranked it as their number one choice, the second is the use of 360-degree feedback that depends on what you are measuring on employee's performance, feedback of employee's performance becomes timely and specifically

followed at number three. The assessment of timeliness and cost-effectiveness of projects was ranked fourth and fifth, last was self-Assessment.

Efficient Methods for Evaluating Productivity in Construction Company

Table 31 Opinion of Respondents Concerning Efficient Methods for Evaluating Productivity

Efficient Methods for Evaluating Productivity	Rank
The measurement of hours worked	1
Input Output tables	2
VAPM can assess accurately productivity	3
Enhancement of the employee's wage	4
The manpower survey method	5
Work sampling method	6

Table 31 shows that most of the respondents ranked the measurement of hours worked as their first choice because it can be the best method for evaluating productivity in the construction company. The second is Input Output tables. VAPM is ranked at number three. The enhancement of the employee's wage was ranked fourth. The manpower survey method and work sampling method followed closely at number five and six, respectively.

Difference in the Perception of the Respondents

To determine if there is any significant difference in the perception of the respondents, regarding the impact of human resource development on employee's performance and productivity in selected construction companies in Metro Manila, t-test was conducted to prove hypothesis.

Table 32 T-test Results on the Difference in Responses When Classified according to Important Factors through HRD on the Employee's Performance

Particular	Mean	t-value	p-value	Sig	Interpretation
Planning	3.54	-1.448	0.07465	0.1492	Not Significant
Team Work Communication	3.53	-1.350	0.08951	0.1790	Not Significant
Organization	3.64	-0.334	0.36934	0.7386	Not Significant
Improvement of Knowledge and Skills	3.72	0.682	0.75209	0.4958	Not Significant
Decision Making	3.79	1.336	0.90851	0.1830	Not Significant
Leadership	3.79	1.353	0.90983	0.1915	Not Significant
Work Processes and Results	3.71	0.386	0.64988	0.7002	Not Significant

Table 32 presents the result of the t-test among groups of the respondents concerning important factors that can affect on employee's performance through HRD. As assumed unequal variances for a two-tailed test, all factors involving planning, team work communication, organization, improvement of knowledge and skills, making decision, leadership, and work processes and results generated t-values of -1.448, -1.35, -0.334, 0.682, 1.336, 1.353, and 0.386 respectively. These t-values were all found to be not significant as shown by the individual sig or probability values greater than 0.05. This further manifest that the perceptions of the respondents did not differ significantly, thus, the (null) hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the perception of the respondents as the impact of HRD on employee's performance. Statistically, there is a strong evidence that shows the relationship between the implementation of HRD on employee's performance and the performance of companies and capability of the ten (10) selected construction companies in Metro Manila.

Table 33 T-test Results on the Difference in Responses When Classified according to Important Factors on the Productivity through HRD

Particular	Mean	t-value	p-value	Sig	Interpretation
Employee's Satisfaction	3.65	0.389	0.65131	0.6974	Not Significant
Workplace Performance	3.63	0.140	0.55568	0.8886	Not Significant
Employee's Wage	3.79	1.560	0.93951	0.1210	Not Significant
Change Of Culture	3.65	0.275	0.60824	0.7836	Not Significant

Table 33 presents the result of t-test among groups of the respondents concerning important factors that can affect the employee's productivity through HRD. As assumed unequal variances for a two-tailed test, all factors involving; Employee's satisfaction, Workplace performance, Employee's wage, and Change of the culture generated t-values of 0.389, 0.140, 1.560, and 0.275 respectively.

These t-values were all found to be not significant as shown by individual sig or probability values greater than 0.05. This further manifest that the perceptions of the respondents did not differ significantly, thus, the (null) hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the perception of the respondents on the impact of HRD on productivity. This suggests that there is a good relationship between the implementation of HRD and productivity on the performance and capability of the ten (10) selected construction companies in Metro Manila.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter summarizes the gathered data and discusses conclusions and recommendations derived from the research study. The hypothesis and research questions found in the statement of the problem are answered by virtue of analysis of observations, researched information and gathered data. Moreover, certain recommendations are offered for future similar research.

Summary

The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of human resource development on employee's performance and productivity in selected construction companies in Metro Manila. The researcher attempted to find the level of awareness of the respondents concerning human resource development in increasing employee's performance and productivity and company profit in the selected construction companies in Metro Manila as perceived by them (the respondents). This study looked into the prospects and challenges posed by HRD on employee's performance. Furthermore, it attempted to know the efficient methods for evaluating employee's performance and productivity, and in large, the influences of human resource development in the construction industry. The study used survey questionnaires as

key research instruments which are all adapted from well known scholars and researchers in the field of HRD. The respondents of this study are limited to ten (10) selected construction companies which are classified an (AAA) located in Metro Manila, Philippines. And from each company five (5) persons (project managers, engineers, construction managers and other experts) were randomly selected to answer the survey questionnaire.

In summary, the basic findings of the study are as follows:

Problem 1

What is the level of awareness of the respondents concerning human resource development in increasing employee's performance and productivity and company profit in the selected construction companies in Metro Manila as perceived by the respondents?

Given are eleven (11) areas of concern in the field of HRD perceived to measure the levels of awareness of the respondents concerning employee's performance and productivity.

- 1) As to most efficient method for training, on-the-job training (OJT) was considered as best method in improving employee's knowledge and ability in the construction industry;
- 2) As to who has most responsibility to develop HR, an HRD director was considered the right person;
- 3) As to the efficient course in construction industry considered important in improving the employee's knowledge and ability, construction project management was considered to be the best option;
- 4) As to the most important area in the organizational development (OD) in improving employee's performance and skills, Strategic Leadership was considered the best option;

- 5) As to the most important goal why there is a need to establish HR in construction industry, the need for improving the quality of output was considered the best option;
- 6) As to the most efficient method for assessing HRD, the evaluation of company profit proved to be the best choice;
- 7) As to the benefits from HRD to employees in construction companies, improvement of skills and reduction of errors in the workplace was considered the best option;
- 8) As to the advantages that employees derive from HRD, the increase of company profit proved to be the best majority choice;
- 9) As to the most important factor for increasing productivity, the improvement of the technical skills and know-how was considered the best option;
- 10) As to the most important factor to increase organizational performance in construction companies, the enhancement of productivity in the company was chosen as best;
- 11) As to important priorities for human capital development in HRD, leadership was chosen the best option.

Problem 2

What are the prospects and challenges of human resource development on employee's performance and productivity in selected construction companies in Metro Manila?

1. On the prospects of human resource development in construction companies, respondents agreed that a) identification and determination of training needs, b) employee's awareness of HR policy, and c) determination of the specific process for the organization development are main prospects of human resource development in construction company.
2. On the challenges of developing human resource in construction company, a) time, b) number of employees, and c) expenses of

training are respectively the challenges in implementing HRD in construction companies.

3. On the impact of HRD on employee's performance and productivity in construction companies, decision-making and leadership abilities have the most influence in improving employee's performance and attitude in the workplace.
4. To boost productivity, a) employee's wage, b) change of culture, c) workplace performance are three best priorities.
5. In terms of rate of changes of employee's performance and productivity during implementation of HRD, it is observed that HRD can improve.
 - a) employee's skills and performance by 11-15 %,
 - b) behavior and attitude by 6-10 % ,
 - c) employee's wage, satisfaction and productivity by 11- 15 %,
 - d) project's completion time reduced by 6-10 %.

Problem 3

What are the efficient methods for evaluating employee's performance and productivity to analyze and understand the influences of human resource development in the construction industry?

The efficient methods for evaluating employee's performance and productivity in construction companies is found to be the **quality of employee's performance**. Second best efficient method for evaluating employee's performance and productivity is **measurement of hours in the workplace**.

There is no significant difference in the perception of the respondents as to the impact of HRD on employee's performance and productivity. Generally, there is a meaningful relationship between HRD and employee's performance and productivity.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the foregoing significant findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Majority of the respondents have high levels of awareness and knowledge about HRD in selected construction companies in Metro Manila, specifically on the eleven areas and disciplines of HR. Most of them ranked on the job training (OJT) as the best method for training in construction companies, HR director has the most responsibility for developing HRD, and construction project management is the best course for managers in construction. Improvement of the employee's performance is the first role of OD and improving quality of output is the most important role of HRD. Determining the profit is the best way to know the effectiveness of HRD. On the other hand, the improvement of employee's performance and increasing profit are the benefits of HRD to employees and companies respectively, increasing OD can mostly increase productivity, and leadership is the first priority for human capital development in HRD.

2. The identification and determination of training needs and the determination of the specific process for the organization development are the main prospects of HRD in construction companies in Metro Manila. Time, number of employees, and cost are the most challenging factors in the implementation of HRD in construction companies in Metro Manila.

3. HRD can improve some factors which are most significant such as leadership and decision-making skills and abilities to promote employee's performance by 11-15% in the construction companies. Employee's wage, change of the culture, and the workplace performance are respectively as the most important factors which can increase productivity through HRD in the workplace by 11-15%. On the other hand, HRD was rated to improve attitude and behavior of the employee by 6-10%. So, the companies can improve more the skills and ability of the employees than their attitude and behavior. It is logical to say that there are other several factors which can improve behavior other than training such as age, family's background, experiences, gender, and others. Also, there is a strong relationship between the implementation of the HRD and employee's performance, and productivity in selected construction companies in Metro Manila.

4. The assessment of quality of employee's performance and the measurement of hours worked are respectively the best methods to evaluate employee's performance and productivity in construction companies that implement HRD.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are offered:

- In view of the fact that there is a high level of awareness concerning the impact of HRD on employee's performance and productivity, the department of HR must take the issue of human resource development (capacity building for performance) seriously and continually as a way of improving employee's performance and productivity to achieve high levels of performance and deliver excellent value for money.
- Inasmuch as OJT (on-the-job) method of training is considered the best option for improving performance and productivity, this method should be used extensively by organizations, especially in the training of junior staff as they tend to be cheaper and more effective. The learning must be about focusing more new information and new behaviors.
- Inasmuch as HRD has a meaningful and good relationship with the employee's performance and productivity as perceived by the respondents HRD should be designed and put in proper mechanisms for monitoring and the establishment of the internal control measures and strengthening for training and the organizational development. Also, the diversity experts identified needs the assessment and evaluation as essential components that contribute to the effectiveness of diversity training programs. This means that HRD professionals need to understand the role of both needs assessment and processes in the success of diversity training.

- Inasmuch as decision-making and leadership skills and abilities are considered top benefits derived from implementation of HRD in construction companies, HR professionals should know more and more about matters concerning how to plan data collection, identify sources of information, develop data collection instruments, analyze information gathered, and report findings for developing HR. Good leadership is essential for effective change in HRD, and this is one of the main themes of this strategy. Managers must be committed to improving HRD at all levels, and to becoming an organization where leaders lead by personal example and inspire others. Leaders must also understand the value of conducting needs assessment and evaluation in HRD and therefore allocate resources for conducting these processes properly.
- The replication of this study to validate its findings is recommended.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Letter of Request

Dear Sir/Madam:

I am Behnam Neyestani, a graduate student of the University of the East – Manila. Presently, I am pursuing a Master of Science degree in Construction Management. As part of the requirements in my graduate program, I am currently completing my thesis entitled **“Human Resource Development on Employee's Performance and Productivity in Selected Construction Companies ”**.

In this regard, may I request permission from your good office to please allow me to conduct my study in your company and be allowed to distribute my survey questionnaires to your selected employees. I promise that any information gathered will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

I hope this request merits your kind consideration and approval.

Thank you very much.

Very truly yours,

BEHNAM NEYESTANI,

Researcher

Noted by:

MELITO A. BACCAY, D. Eng.

Research Adviser

Noted:

JULIAN E. ABUSO, Ph.D

Dean, UE Graduate School

APPENDIX B

Survey Questionnaire

Dear respondents,

Attached are details of the survey questionnaire regarding human resource development on employee's performance and productivity in construction companies in Metro Manila, Philippines. We would like to ask your participation in giving your ideas by answering the question as objectively as possible in order to achieve progressive knowledge regarding the subject.

Instruction: please put a **check** mark on the space provided that best corresponds to your answer.

Thank you very much,

The Researcher

PART ONE

Personal Background

Name: _____(optional)

Gender: Male Female

Civil Status: single married

separated widowed

Age: below 20 20-29

30-39 40-49

50 and above

Work Experience in Construction Industry:

one year 1-3 years 3-5 years

5-8 years 8-10 years 13

Educational Background:

OND/NCE/Other Diploma Higher Degree Msc/MA

Associate PH.D./Professional

B.Sc./B.A.

Level of Education:

Project Manager Executive Manager

Supervisor

Length of Training Experience in a Training Program

Short term OJT, one month or less

Moderate term OJT, 1-12 months

[] Long term OJT, more than a year

Kind of Methods of Training Experience:

[] on the job training

[] seminar and conference

[] self directed learning

[] presentation method, Internet

[] others

PART II

(SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FORM)

For determination of the level of awareness of individuals (managers, engineers, superintendents and other experts) concerning implementation of human resource development on employees performance and productivity in construction companies in Metro Manila, Philippines.

Instruction: Please choose just three (3) of the following options which are most importantly for you.

The level of the respondent's awareness on human resource development and its impact toward employee's performances and productivity in selected construction companies in Metro Manila as perceived by the respondents:

1. By your experience, what kind of methods of training are the most efficient and economical for improving skills and behavior of employees in your company?

Mentoring/Coaching	
On the job training	
Presentation method such as Internet and CD-ROM	
Seminars	
Conferences	
Self-directed learning	
Others	

2. Who are the most responsible concerning HRD in construction company?

President of the company	
contractor	
Project manager	
Executive manager	
HR director	
Vice president of the company	
Others	

3. What kind of courses are the most suitable for you to become more efficient in your company to improve your knowledge and ability in your construction company?

Construction project management	
Construction project cost management	
Construction new methods and technology management	
Construction project time management	
Construction project material management	
Construction project quality management	
Others	

4. Which following items are the most important for organizational development (OD) toward the improvement of skills, employee's performance and productivity in the company?

IT (Information technology)	
Statistical process control	
Management of change	
Strategic leadership	
System analysis and design	

Creative problem solving and making decision	
Others	

5. Which of the following reasons are the most important in establishing the HRD?	
Changes in technology	
Need to train more to remain competitive	
New hires did not have necessary skills, ability and behavior	
Need to improve employee's performance and productivity	
Need to improve the quality of your output	
Changes in the organization of work	
Others	

6. What kind of assessment are the most efficient for the HRD in construction company?	
Financial assessment such as Return-on-Investment (ROI)	
Evaluating profit of the company	
Evaluating employee's skills and behavior	
Computing expences of project before and after HRD for	

employees	
Time assessment in project	
Quality assessment in project	
Others	

7. What are the benefits of HRD on employees ?	
Increasing the salary of employee	
Increasing safety and reduction of injury in the workplace	
Learning how to work with new methods and ways toward increasing productivity	
provement of skills and attitude and reduction of error in the workplace	
Improvement of employee's satisfaction and employer's satisfaction from employee's performance in the company	
Promotion of employee's level and position in the company	
Others	

8. What are the benefits of HRD for construction companies?	
Increasing profit for the company	
Increasing productivity	

Competing with other companies	
Administrating and controlling the projects as well as with employees who improved their knowledge and skills by HRD	
Getting customer's satisfaction by doing project on time and quality	
Using new and high method and technology can be possible toward reduction of costs	
Others	

9. From the following items, what items do you think are the most important in increasing productivity through HRD in construction company?	
Changing the company culture	
Improving moral and attitude in the workplace	
Reduction of time in project	
Reduction of the costs of company	
Improving technical skills and knowledge	
Improving job satisfaction	
Others	

10. From the following items, what items do you think are the most significant in increasing organizational performance in construction companies?	
Increasing the assets of construction company	
Enhancement of productivity in the company	
Reduction of the costs of company	
Increasing customer's satisfaction	
Improving technical skills and knowledge	
Reduction of time in project	
Others	

11. Which of the following priorities are significant for human capital development in HRD?	
Strategic skills/competencies	
Strategic integration	
Strategic alignment	
Reengineering the human resources function	
Culture/strategic awareness	
Leadership	
Others	

PART III
(SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FORM)

The objective of this section is to identify aspects, challenges and identification of the factors that Influence employee's performance and productivity in Manila, the Philippines.

Please indicate your answers to each of the question by just putting a check mark [√] on the box that describes your best answer:

Table with 5 columns: Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, Strongly Agree

Prospects of human resource development in construction company

Table with 2 main rows for questions and 5 columns for ratings (1-5)

3	Are training needs identified through a formal performance appraisal mechanism for increasing firm performances in the company?					
4	Should your company use a specific organization development process?					
5	Are training needs identified realistic, useful and based on the business strategy?					
6	Should top managers engage training and organization development activities for him /herself and others in the company?					
7	Should formal training programs exist to teach new employees and the skills that they need to perform their jobs to improve employee's performances and productivity in the company ?					
8	Should your management encourage you to join any training and self-development programs?					
9	Does your top management take feedback to know the effects of HRD in your company?					
10	Does human resource development have benefits for employees and companies?					
11	Do you feel attach with your company, team and other employees after developing human resource in your company?					
12	Has training and organization development influenced your desire to stay in the company?					

13	Can you be promoted in your position and level by OD and learning new skills?					
14	Can human resource development help construction companies in performing their projects at a minimum cost and time?					

The challenges of developing human resource in construction company

No.	The challenges of developing human resource in construction company					
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Is the cost of training and OD a barrier in expanding and establishing HRD in the company?					
2	Is it difficult to find a proper and suitable training program and OD strategy for employees in the construction company?					
3	Is it a big problem for manpower training if employees dont have enough time to learn and improve their skills in the workplace?					
4	Are the motivation and employee’s interest a big problem to improve employee’s skills and knowledge through HRD in your company?					
5	Is the implementation of HRD not justifiable when the number of employees is too small?					
6	Is it difficult to find competent trainers and suitable OD strategy in					

	construction companies?					
7	Is it a big challenge for construction companies to implement an efficient method to measure and understand improving employee's performance after and before HRD in the company?					
8	Is it difficult to find and enforce a proper OD strategy by manager in construction industry?					

The impact of human resource development on employee's performance

No.	The impact of human resource development on employee's performance					
		1	2	3	4	5
	– Planning					
1	Does the employee set verifiable short- and long-term goals through HRD?					
2	Can HRD help the employee's goals attached with company needs?					
3	Does the employee's planning show sound assumptions reflecting the company's goals and resources by improvement of HRD?					
4	Does the employee typically achieve expected results according to the plans of HRD?					
	– Team work communication					

5	Employee's commitment in the organization is enhanced by human resource development of					
6	Does HRD improve communication skills of employees and team work in the company?					
7	Can HRD properly help the employees to interact with external environment in the company?					
	– Organization					
8	Is human resource development in the organization in terms of frequency of on-the-job training enhances employees'performance?					
9	Is the recruitment and selection processes in the organisation are impartial through HRD?					
10	Can OD give enough knowledge to the employee on what the organization can do in case of emergency?					
11	Does the organizational development really inspire the employee in performing their jobs?					
	– Improve knowledge, skills and attitude					
12	Is training system able to improve HR outcomes in construction companies?					
13	Are employees able to improve behavior and attitude by training and OD in their organization?					
14	Is human resources development impacted well on the skills and experiences of staffs?					

15	Does the employee see better relationships between facts and draw appropriate conclusions quickly?					
16	Does the employee perform well in the absence of superiors after enforcement of HRD?					
17	Has the employee made original suggestions to improve operations after training and development?					
-Decision- Making						
18	Can training and OD help to improve managers in making decision in construction company?					
19	When confronted with an emergency, can the employee quickly recognize the most important priorities through HRD?					
20	Does HRD teach staffs how to make an exact decision through improvement employee's performace?					
21	Does HRD help the employee to make decisions accurately more after training and OD ?					
- Leadership						
22	Do training and OD help managers how to control employees in the organization?					
23	Do people listen closely when managers speak after enforcement of training ?					
24	Does HRD help employees and leadership to have a good relationship in the organization?					
25	By HRD, do managers deal smoothly with unexpected developments in HR?					
- Work processes and results						
26	Can employees reduce their failures and errors after learning and					

	improving their skills and knowledge by training and OD in the company?					
27	Can employees do their performances faster after learning and improving their skills and knowledge by training and OD in the company?					
28	Can HRD improve the quality of employee's performance in the organization?					

Impact of human resource development on organizational performance and productivity

No.	The impact of human resource development on organization performance and productivity					
		1	2	3	4	5
	– Employee's satisfaction					
1	Are the employees of the construction company satisfied with increasing the quality of their skills and knowledge toward increasing productivity by HRD?					
2	Can the organization development improve the satisfaction of employee through HRD?					
3	Are you satisfied that you have the opportunities to apply your talents and expertise?					
4	Are you pleased with the training and OD that give career advancement opportunities to you?					

5	Does the training system help to reduce absenteeism in your construction company?					
6	Can the improvement of employee's morale increase productivity in the company?					
	– Workplace performance (Organization performance)					
7	Is HRD able to improve organization performance in construction companies?					
8	Are construction companies able to reduce the time of completion of their projects by implementing human resource development in increasing productivity?					
9	Can human resource development help to increase quality of your construction company?					
10	Are the companies able to increase the ratio output to Input or productivity by applying training and OD for employees in construction toward increasing efficiency?					
11	Does the HRD reduce employee's turnover toward increasing productivity?					
12	Does the HRD increase client's satisfaction in increasing productivity?					
13	Does the HRD increase the profitability of your company ?					
	– Employee's wage					
14	Can training and OD help in increasing the wage of employees in construction company?					

15	Is the company able to increase profit by applying training and OD in the organization?					
16	Is wage as a proxy of productivity in any company where HRD has done to employees?					
	– Change of culture					
17	Can human resource development help to change the culture of construction company to use new methods and technology for the improvement of productivity?					
18	Do you feel loyalty to the organisation after developing human resource in increasing productivity?					
19	Do you feel a strong sense of 'belonging' to your organisation after developing human resource toward increasing productivity ?					

The rate of changes of employee's Performance and Productivity through Human Resource Development In Construction Companies

No.	The rate of changes of employee's performance through HRD	0 -5%	6 -10%	11-15%	More than 15%
1	What is the percentage of improving employee's skills and ability after developing human resource in your company?				
2	What is the percentage of improving employee's				

	behavior and attitude after establishing HRD in your company?				
3	What is the percentage of improving employee's performance after training and development in your company?				
No.	The rate of changes of organization performance and productivity through HRD	0-5%	6 -10%	11-15%	More than 15%
4	What is the percentage of improving employee's satisfaction after developing human resource in your company?				
5	What is the percentage of increasing employee's wage after developing human resource in your company?				
6	What is the percentage of reduction on project's completion time after developing human resource in your company?				
7	What is the percentage of increasing productivity in the organization after developing human resource in your company?				

Determination of the Efficient Methods to Measure Employee's Performance and Productivity to Analyze the Impact of Human Resource Development In Construction Industry

The efficient methods for evaluating employee's performance in construction company	
The assessment of timeliness and cost-effectiveness of projects	
Self-Assessment	
Using 360-degree feedback that depends on what you are measuring of employee's performance	
Feedback of employee's performance become timely and specifically	
The assessment of quality of employee's performance and amount error of employee in the workplace	

The efficient methods for evaluating productivity in construction company	
Enhancement of the employee's wage	
VAPM can assess accurately productivity	
Work sampling method	
The manpower survey method	
The measurement of hours worked	
Input Output tables	